

國立高雄科技大學

國際管理碩士學位學程

碩士論文

影響消費者對 BOPIS（在線購買店內提貨）態度和行為意向的因素

越南雜貨採購案例研究

**Factors affecting consumer attitude and behavioral intention
towards BOPIS (Buy online pick up in-store)
A case study on grocery purchase in Viet Nam**

研究生: 黎氏垂楊/Le Thi Thuy Duong

指導教授: 郭幸民 博士 Shin Ming Guo

中華民國 111 年 09 月

影響消費者對 BOPIS (在線購買店內提貨) 態度和行為意向的因素

越南雜貨採購案例研究

**Factors affecting consumer attitude and behavioral intention
towards BOPIS (Buy online pick up in-store)
A case study on grocery purchase in Viet Nam**

研究生: 黎氏垂楊/Le Thi Thuy Duong

指導教授: 郭幸民 博士 Shin Ming Guo

國立高雄科技大學

國際管理碩士學位學程

碩士論文

A Thesis Submitted to
The Department of International Master Business Administration
College of Management
National Kaohsiung University of Science and Technology
in Partial Fulfillment of the Requirements
for the Degree of Master

September 2022

Yanchao, Kaohsiung, Taiwan, Republic of China

中華民國 111 年 09 月

Factors affecting consumer attitude and behavioral intention towards BOPIS
(Buy online pick up in-store)
A case study on grocery purchase in Viet Nam

Student: Le Thi Thuy Duong

Advisors: Shin Ming Guo

The International Master of Business Administration (IMBA) Department of the
College of Management

National Kaohsiung University of Science and Technology

ABSTRACT

We conduct a study based on consumer characteristics and perceptions through the data collected from 203 respondents who are Vietnamese to understand about the factors affecting to their attitude and behavioral intention towards BOPIS (buy online pick up in-store) for grocery purchase. The study applied many typical analytical methods which include Confirmation Factor Analysis (CFA) and Structural Equation Model (SEM). The analyses finally figured out the effects of consumer's perceived benefit (*online information, offline physical experience, flexibility, time and effort saving, shipping fee saving, easy returns and refunds, and product original condition*) and the perceived ease of use (*clear and understandable process, ease to use online system, ease to learn using online system, ease to access the physical store, simple process, and ease to be mastered* in shopping with BOPIS) are the factors effecting to consumer attitude and behavioral intention towards BOPIS for grocery purchase. At the same time, consumer attitude was proved to have mediating effect in the model. The perceived risk (*privacy risk, financial risk, information risk, product risk, and performance risk*) was not found to have significant effect on consumer attitude and behavioral intention but *BOPIS experience* influences on the relationship of the perceived risk and consumer's attitude as a moderating factor. In addition, the study had some other interesting analyses on consumer's intention in using BOPIS that consist of the intention in using the service to purchase different categories of grocery. Besides, the study also predicted the adoption of the service in Vietnam market.

Keywords: BOPIS, buy online pick up in-store, grocery shopping, Vietnamese consumers, attitude, behavioral intention, perceived benefit, perceived ease of use, perceived risk, BOPIS experience.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

I would like to express my sincere appreciation to all those who contributed to this study. The first and most respectful thank goes to my advisor, Professor Shin-Ming Guo, who has been working with me since the very beginning of the thesis when it was just an idea, who gave me a lot of his patience and helpful advice that step by step guided me for the thesis improvement and fulfilment. I also would like to express my deep gratefulness to National Kaohsiung University of Science and Technology (NKUST) as well as the International Master of Business Administration (IMBA) Department that offered me the opportunity to pursue my master degree and gave me such a great and professional study environment. Thank you to all of the respondents who engaged in the survey to help me get the data for analysis. Thanks for my friend supports and my family encouragement which help me overcome difficulties and keep motivation to complete this study. Finally, although this thesis still has its shortcomings, it is the result of my own effort and everyone's contributions, hopefully it can be well acclaimed.

TABLE OF CONTENTS

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION	1
1.1 BACKGROUND	1
1.2 RESEARCH OBJECTIVE	2
1.3 RESEARCH SCOPE AND SUBJECT	3
CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEWS	5
2.1 UNDERSTANDING OF BOPIS	5
2.2 REVIEWS OF OUTSTANDING FUNDAMENTAL THEORIES ABOUT CONSUMER BEHAVIORAL INTENTION AND RESEARCHES RELATED BOPIS BEHAVIORAL INTENTION	8
CHAPTER 3: HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT	14
3.1 PROPOSAL RESEARCH FRAMEWORK	14
3.2 HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT	14
3.3 DESCRIPTION AND MEASUREMENT OF VARIABLES:	18
CHAPTER 4: METHODOLOGY	22
4.1 DATA ANALYSIS METHOD	22
4.1.1 Describe the data by Descriptive statistics.....	22
4.1.2 Checking the differences among intentions of using BOPIS to purchase difference categories of grocery by using Paired samples T test.....	22
4.1.3 Check reliability of the measurement by Cronbach’s Alpha	22
4.1.4 Structural Equation Model (SEM) to find out the factors and their relationships.....	23
4.1.4.1 Confirmation Factor Analysis (CFA)	23
4.1.4.2 Investigate the relationships among factors by path analysis	24
4.1.4.3 Test mediating effect in SEM by using bootstrapping.....	24
4.1.4.4 Test moderation in SEM by using Multigroup Analysis	24
4.1.4.5 SEM evaluation indices	25
4.2 DATA ANALYSIS TOOLS	25
4.3 DATA COLLECTION METHOD	26
4.3.1 Sample size	26
4.3.2 Measurement scales	26
4.3.3 Sampling method	26
CHAPTER 5: ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION	27
5.1 UNDERSTANDING OF THE SAMPLE	27
5.1.1 General information	28
5.1.2 Grocery shopping habit.....	30
5.1.3 BOPIS knowledge and experience.....	31
5.1.4 BOPIS intention for grocery purchase	32
5.1.4.1 Probability that consumers use BOPIS to purchase groceries.....	32
5.1.4.2 Purchase intention based on product categories/characteristics	33
5.2 FACTORS AFFECTING CONSUMER ATTITUDE AND BEHAVIORAL INTENTION TOWARDS BOPIS FOR GROCERY PURCHASE	36
5.2.1 Confirmation factor analysis (CFA).....	36
5.2.2 Investigate the effects of factors on consumer attitude and behavioral intention.....	44
5.2.2.1 The causal relationships among factors	44

5.2.2.2 Test the mediating effect of the Attitude.....	46
5.2.2.3 Test the moderating effect of BOPIS knowledge and BOPIS experience	47
CHAPTER 6: CONCLUSION	50
6.1 SUMMARY	50
6.2 IMPLICATION	51
6.2.1 Vietnamese consumer characteristics and the potential of BOPIS for grocery purchase in Vietnam	51
6.2.2 Consumer intention to use BOPIS for grocery purchase and the effect of product category	51
6.2.3 Factors affecting consumer attitudes and behavioral intentions towards BOPIS for grocery purchase	52
6.3 COMPARISON TO OTHER PREVIOUS RESEARCHES	53
6.4 RESEARCH LIMITATION AND FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTION	54
REFERENCES	56
Appendix 1 Survey Questionnaire	62
Appendix 2 Data output	68
1. Data description	68
2. Paired Samples T Test	82
3. Cronbach’s Alpha	82
4. CFA	84
4.1 Factor Analysis result:	84
4.2 Measurement Model and outputs used to create validity and reliability estimates:.....	87
5. Causal model	91
6. Outputs for testing mediating effect of the Attitude	92
7. Outputs for testing moderating effects of BOPIS knowledge and experience	93

LIST OF FIGURES

Figure 1.1 Research time schedule	4
Figure 2.1 Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) Model	9
Figure 2.2 Theory of Stimulus-Organism-Response (S-O-R) model	9
Figure 2.3 Model of Consumer Behavior from Kotler and Armstrong	10
Figure 2.4 Factors Influencing Consumer Behavior by Kotler and Armstrong.....	10
Figure 2.5 Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)	11
Figure 2.6 Extended valence framework (EVF).....	11
Figure 3.1 The proposal framework	14
Figure 5.1 Distribution of consumers' consensus level on using BOPIS to purchase packaged food product	34
Figure 5.2 Distribution of consumers' consensus level on using BOPIS to purchase fresh and refrigerated food product	34
Figure 5.3 Distribution of consumers' consensus level on using BOPIS to purchase non-food product....	35
Figure 5.4 Scree plot and Eigenvalue of factor analysis.....	39
Figure 5.5 The measurement model of CFA	40
Figure 5.6 The causal model of research.....	44

LIST OF TABLES

Table 3.1 Table of Hypotheses and investigated relationships.....	17
Table 3.2 Description and measurement of variables.....	19
Table 4.1 Standards for the fit of model.....	25
Table 5.1 The general description of data	27
Table 5.2 General information of the sample	29
Table 5.3 Frequency that consumers go grocery shopping	30
Table 5.4 Online grocery shopping experience	30
Table 5.5 Priority channel for grocery shopping.....	31
Table 5.6 BOPIS knowledge and experience	32
Table 5.7 Probability that consumers use BOPIS to purchase groceries.....	33
Table 5.8 The consensus level of using BOPIS to purchase different grocery categories.....	33
Table 5.9 Paired differences of the consensus level of using BOPIS to purchase a particular category of grocery products with the other one.	36
Table 5.10 The result of Cronbach's Alpha	37
Table 5.11 The result of Rotated Component Matrix.....	38
Table 5.12 The estimates to check reliability and validity of measurement.....	43
Table 5.13 Regression Weights of the causal model.....	44
Table 5.14 Covariances among variables	45
Table 5.15 The bootstrapping result of indirect and direct effects of factors on BI under the AT mediator	47
Table 5.16 The Moderation test for BOPIS knowledge and BOPIS experience	48
Table 5.17 Regression weights of unconstrained model for effect of PR → AT under BOPIS experience moderator	49

CHAPTER 1: INTRODUCTION

1.1 BACKGROUND

Along with the developments of science and technology, human being lives are increasingly improved. Especially, the Internet and Logistic revolutions have created a new era which the distance among people is shortened, everything becomes faster and more convenient. Accordingly, the emergence of E-commerce is gradually changing people's perception of trade and commerce, people nowadays do not need to come physical stores but are still able to make their purchases via the internet just by clicks. Consumers prefer online shopping because it brings them convenience, large selection of products, advantages of information, price or promotion (Shanthi & Kannaiah, 2015; Singhal & Patra, 2018; Kaur, 2018). However, online stores can not completely replace the role of traditional stores. Brick-and-mortar stores still prevail in terms of physical experience, available products/services and low risk (Gupta *et al.*, 2013; Sarkar, 2017). Retailers try to develop their E-commerce to increase sales and support for the traditional channels, meanwhile giant E-commerce businesses like Amazon or Alibaba have been opening their chains of physical stores to serve customers better. Thus, in this E-commerce era, traditional stores have not been disappeared but growing strongly in various dimensions, both online and offline channel thrive in parallel to support and complement the shortcomings of each other.

The concept of omnichannel was born by Rigby (2011) and became well-known in marketing field. It indicates strategies of integrating variety of channels, which including online and offline ones, to provide customers seamless shopping experience and lead them to purchase behavior. *Buy online pickup in-store* (BOPIS), another term for *click and collect*, is one of the most popular form of omnichannel retail strategies that consumers to go shopping and place orders online, then go to the brick-and-mortar stores to pick up their purchase. On another hand, a similar concept to omnichannel is O2O (*online to offline*) commerce which was first coined by Rampell (2010). O2O refers to a new commerce model that finds consumers online and brings them into real-world stores. Shari *et al.* (2015), after his synthesizing of many studies on O2O, indicated the types of O2O business model, one of them is *buy online pick up in-store*.

BOPIS nowadays becomes a trend and is applied successfully by retailers in various industries, including grocery retailing. For grocery segment, there is another term of BOPIS is OGP (*Online grocery pickup*). Walmart is the top retailer of *in-store pick up* for the grocery by offering curbside or in-store pickup of online orders at thousands of Walmart locations across the U.S and worldwide. Some other grocery retailers outstanding with *click and collect* service are Kroger, Target, Walgreens, etc. The giant E-commerce Amazon for its grocery segment has also developed its chain of physical stores called Amazon Fresh and Whole Foods Market offered the similar service. Meanwhile, in the other side of globe, Alibaba has been working on the New Retail strategy which part of it

is the chain of FreShippo stores selling grocery products, *pick up in-store* is also one of their delivery options.

In Viet Nam, the changing in people's living conditions and especially the impact of Covid-19 Pandemic recently have led some changes in shopping habit of Vietnamese consumers. According to a survey of Nielsen (2020), 50% of Vietnamese are more hesitated to be at crowded places like markets, supermarkets or grocery stores. They increase stocking food and necessities at home as well as go shopping online more than before. To adapt to the trend, on the commerce platforms of outstanding grocery retailers such as Co.op Mart, Bach Hoa Xanh, Go!, Vinmart and so on have already offered online shopping with door-to-door delivery service. As a result, online retailing has been remarkably growing up over the recent years. The traditional grocery retailing however still dominates with 92% share of the total grocery market, and Vietnam's modern trade penetration in groceries is still low (McKinsey & Company, 2019). Vietnam modern grocery market is predicted to be fast growing in the next few years but currently it is still in its early days so the role of brick-and-mortar stores along with traditional shopping method are still crucial.

BOPIS is supposed to facilitate both retailers and consumers in many aspects and solve many problems that either offline or online channel is dealing with. It is a new model of E-commerce and has started to be applied in Vietnam for some fields which outstandingly are catering or mobile phone and electronic device retailing. Nevertheless, Vietnamese grocery retailers have not widely offered this kind of service and there are neither many studies researching on the potential of BOPIS in Vietnam market. Understanding about consumers is necessary to predict their adoption to BOPIS for grocery purchase. Moreover, finding out the factors affecting to consumer attitude and behavioral intention is helpful to provide solutions to make consumers better adopt the service for grocery purchase in Viet Nam as well as it is good for retailers in BOPIS application to optimize the effectiveness of their omnichannel sales. Those are all the reasons and motivation for this study to be conducted.

1.2 RESEARCH OBJECTIVE

1.2.1 General objectives:

The general objective of this study is to understand and figure out the Vietnamese consumer attitude and behavioral intention towards BOPIS for grocery purchase along with the affecting factors, based on analyses of data collected from consumers about their characteristics and perceptions so that find out the key factors needed to be concerned in the application of grocery BOPIS in Vietnam market.

1.2.2 Specific objectives:

Firstly, this study is expected to be able to predict the potential and adoption of BOPIS for grocery purchase in Vietnam market through understanding about Vietnamese consumers based on the collected information about their characteristics, grocery shopping behaviors and their overall intention of using BOPIS to purchase groceries.

Secondly, this study hopes to find out all of the related consumer behavioral intentions, attitudes and the effecting factors by using Confirmation Factor Analysis (CFA). By the use of CFA, the elements contributing to each factor which are reliable and valid will be determined, the factors will be confirmed.

Thirdly, the relationships among factors would be investigated by the use of Structural Equation Model (SEM) from which the factors really impact on consumer attitude and consumer behavioral intention will be figured out. Through that retailers will know the key factors which need to be concerned to improve the adoption of grocery BOPIS in Vietnam.

Last but not least, by achieving all the above objectives, this study could provide some useful inferences for retailers about the application BOPIS in Vietnam. This study after all can be a reliable source of reference for grocery retailers and future researches.

1.3 RESEARCH SCOPE AND SUBJECT

1.3.1 Space:

This study is conducted in Taiwan, all information and data are collected in Vietnam through an online survey.

1.3.2 Time: The study lasts for 10 months from December 01st 2021 to September 30th 2022. The specified schedule is in the *figure 1.1* below.

1.3.3 Subject:

- *The study subject:* Vietnamese attitude and behavioral intention towards BOPIS for grocery purchase and *the factors affecting* them.
- *The survey subject:* this study surveys on Vietnamese consumers in general who have grocery shopping experience. However, because of the feature of an online survey, the respondents must be internet and social media users to be able to approach the questionnaire.

Figure 1.1 Research time schedule

CHAPTER 2: LITERATURE REVIEWS

2.1 UNDERSTANDING OF BOPIS

According to Leach (2019), the click and collect concept enables shoppers to purchase items online and then pick them up in store, merging e-commerce and brick-and-mortar. With this service, consumers can make their purchase comfortably at their own place, and collect the item whenever is most convenient for them, so that they do not need to pay for shipping fees or wait for the delivery to arrive. Click and collect services are separated into 4 main types:

- 1) *In-store retail click and collect.*
- 2) *In-store lockers.*
- 3) *Remote pickup.* For example: UPS, FedEx, or post offices.
- 4) *Ship-to-store:* The items which are not in stock of a local store can be shipped from a distribution center to have them available for customers to pick up.

BigCommerce (2021) states that BOPIS stands for *buy online pick up in-store* which allows retailers to blend the online and in-store experience to engage with customers while offering a more convenient way to shop. BOPIS has its cousins including:

- 1) *Curbside pickup:* Customers pick up their items outside of the store.
- 2) *BORIS (Buy online return in-store):* Customers buy items online but can go to the stores for product return.
- 3) *ROPIS (Reserve online pick up in-store):* Customers order items online but not really pay for them until they pick up the items.

Damen (2022) supposes that BOPIS is also referred to as *click and collect*, *curbside pickup*, and *ROPIS* (reserve online pick up in-store) which is an ideal strategy for retail stores by integrating both online shopping and in-person pickup. This strategy provides the comfort and convenience of shopping at home and collecting items at store that benefits both retailers and customers.

BOPIS process:

The buying process of BOPIS inferred from large retailers' platforms such as Amazon.com, Walmart.com, Kroger.com, etc. consists of three common stages:

Step 1: Customers purchase online via the retailer's website or mobile app.

This stage is simply carried out like normal online shopping. However, customers should be mindful to select the in-store pickup option at checkout and choose the time as well as the store location for picking up the products.

Step 2: The retailer fulfills the order and notifies the customers

The retailer is in charge of having the online ordered items ready for customers to pick up by the time they arrive the pickup location. It is then also the responsibility of the retailer to notify the customers about their order fulfillment via e-mail or text sent to their purchase account.

Step 3: The customers pick up the order

Customers arrive the store with the notification message or confirmation number to identity their orders, then just pick up the items and go.

BOPIS payment method:

Given those big grocery retailers' webpages, there is a fact that they all have their own payment policies, but in general digital payment methods such as credit/debit cards, digital wallets, checking accounts or EBT cards are preferred instead of cash payment for online or pickup grocery orders. It also means that almost no payment with cash option is offered on their payment method section.

This is quite understandable, according to Ricoh USA Inc. (2020), retailers in developed countries like the US add digital shopping enhancements including BOPIS in recent years as a form of e-commerce because they are supported well by advanced technologies and payment systems. Besides, there is a recent evolution of cashless payment deriving from various reasons including the protection of human health, especially since covid-19 pandemic. It is anticipated to have a cashless economy in the near future. Mar Negreiro (2020) also predicts a cashless society due to the rise of e-commerce. Although Vietnam is known as a developing country but it is dramatically growing, especially in the field of e-commerce and online payment which thank to high cashless payment adoption rate and the improvement of digital payment infrastructure. According to Vietnamplus (2021) the rate of Vietnamese users making mobile payment surprisingly reaches 29.1 percent, ranked the third-highest in the world just after China and Korea. Moreover, making payment in advance through online system is also to make sure that the orders are real and customers will show up at the store to pick up their items. To those reasons, businesses are actively avoiding taking cash payment. Thus, in the event BOPIS is applied in Vietnam for grocery purchases, this study believes that it would emerge with the equivalent mode as what businesses in the world are currently applying.

BOPIS definition for this study:

In general, this study found that the concepts related to making orders online and coming to the selected site for the item pickup are supposed as *buy online pick up in-store* (BOPIS). With this definition, making payment for the grocery purchases should be done before customers come to the site for the item pickup by any digital payment modes. Picking up the items can be done even inside or outside of the stores according to retailers' offering, for instance in-store pickup counters, pickup lockers or curbside.

BOPIS benefits:

BOPIS is expected to benefit both retailers and customers in many aspects. Damen (2022) states that the typical benefits for retailers and consumers include:

Benefits for retailers	Benefits for consumers
1. <i>Increase store traffic and sales:</i> by attracting consumers to the store, they	1. <i>No shipping costs:</i> Sometimes delivery fees can be more expensive than the cost

Benefits for retailers	Benefits for consumers
<p>may spend more time at the store, browse for more products and spend more money. That helps to increase retailers' sales.</p> <p>2. <i>Reduce shipping costs</i>: bulk shipments from distribution center to retailers' stores can help to reduce retailers' shipping costs and consumers pick up order at the store can also help to save some last-mile shipping costs for retailers.</p> <p>3. <i>Improve inventory management</i>: BOPIS helps retailers easily track inventory thanks to getting real-time stock updates, flexibly control and adjust inventory to adapt to demand</p>	<p>that consumers get to the store for picking up the items by themselves. Consumers can save the shipping fee by using BOPIS in this case.</p> <p>2. <i>Speedy service</i>: Consumers can possess the products quickly at any time they want after their purchase without waiting for delivery.</p> <p>3. <i>Guarantee that the item is in stock</i>: that means the items which customers want to buy are ensured to be available at the store and ready to be picked up when they arrive.</p> <p>4. <i>Quick returns and exchanges</i>: If there is any problem with the products consumers can request for returns or exchanges right at the store without waiting to ship the order back or for the replies from retailers.</p>

In fact, there are still many other benefits of BOPIS that make retailers change to apply the service for their omnichannel strategy and consumers change to use the service for their purchase instead of just using pure online shopping.

Online shopping was born to facilitate consumers in the shopping process by offering the convenience, large selection of products, advantages of information, price or promotion (Shanthi & Kanniah, 2015; Singhal & Patra, 2018; Kaur, 2018). However, pure online shopping with its door-to-door delivery process has many risks and inconvenience making consumers hesitate to use this shopping channel (Tham *et al.*, 2019; Masoud, 2013).

According to all of the above features of BOPIS, this study found 3 main advantages of using BOPIS compared to using pure online shopping that can make consumers change to use the service:

- *More convenience and flexibility*: Online shopping is only convenient and flexible in term of making order because consumers can make their purchase at anywhere and anytime they want. However, in order to receive the real items, they need to wait for the delivery. The delivery process can take several days. The delivery can be delayed and the packages even can be lost during that process. As the result, buyers have to passively wait for their order without knowing exactly the time they can receive it. By using BOPIS, buyers can know exactly the time their order is ready and go to the most convenient place at the most convenient time selected by them to pick up their items.

- *More safety*: Financial risk, product risk, delivery risk, return policy risk and information security risk are typical risks of online shopping (Tham *et al.*, 2019; Masoud, 2013). BOPIS can help buyers proactively avoid some of those risks, especially the risk of product and delivery process. Buyers are able to possess the product in its original condition without worrying about product damage or loss deriving from delivery process. Buyers are also able to check the product condition and quality when receiving the items from staffs and easily request to return or exchange for another one, in the event those products are not qualified or meet their requirement. Moreover, the existence of physical stores strengthens the confidence for buyers not to be cheated by bogus online stores. Consequently, they can avoid many possible losses deriving from pure online shopping.
- *More enjoyment*: By using BOPIS, buyers not only enjoy the pleasure of online shopping like comfortably browsing or selecting the products at home but also can experience the feeling of seeing and touching the products or interacting with staffs and other people when they come to the store to pick up their order. Buyer can even spend more time at the store just for “window shopping” or making more purchase if they want. That is much more delightful than just clicking and waiting for order delivery as pure online shopping.

2.2 REVIEWS OF OUTSTANDING FUNDAMENTAL THEORIES ABOUT CONSUMER BEHAVIORAL INTENTION AND RESEARCHES RELATED BOPIS BEHAVIORAL INTENTION

In order to develop the conceptual framework and hypotheses for a research on consumer behavioral intention as what this study is aiming at, a range of literature reviews have been done. Many outstanding theories about consumer behavior which became popular and fundamental as of Fishbein & Ajzen (1975), Kotler & Armstrong (2014), David (1989) or Kim *et al.* (2009). There are also a great number of studies on consumer intentions towards choosing shopping channels including O2O or BOPIS which were developed based on those theories and had many interesting findings. The followings are details about the outstanding theories and researches along with their notable findings which are considered important and fundamental for the conceptual framework and the hypotheses of this research developed in *chapter 3*:

❖ **Fishbein & Ajzen (1975) - Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA):**

TRA states that the *behavioral intention* precedes the *actual behavior* and it is affected by the *attitude* towards that behavior and the *subjective norms*. *Attitude* towards a certain behavior can be positive, negative or neutral and influenced by the *behavioral beliefs* and the *outcomes evaluation*.

Figure 2.1 Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) Model

Source: Fishbein & Ajzen (1975)

❖ **Woodworth (1929) – Theory of Stimulus-Organism-Response (S-O-R):**

The theory was first proposed by Woodworth in 1929 that simply explained someone’s behavioral responses (R) are usually affected by the individual internal assessments or emotions (O), which is derived from stimuli (S).

Figure 2.2 Theory of Stimulus-Organism-Response (S-O-R) model

Source: Woodworth (1929)

❖ **Kotler & Armstrong (2014) - Theory of Consumer Behavior and Black Box model:**

The Black Box model is one of the models developed from the S-O-R theory of Woodworth (1929). The theory of Consumer Behavior and the Black Box model are mentioned in the book of Kotler and Armstrong (2014) related marketing aspect that specifies the 4 Ps marketing stimuli (product, price, place and promotion) and some other environment factors (economic, technological, social and cultural) affect to the buyer’s black box and lead to buyer different responses including buyer’s *attitudes* and related *behaviors*.

Figure 2.3 Model of Consumer Behavior from Kotler and Armstrong
 Source: Kotler & Armstrong (2014)

Also according to the Kotler & Armstrong (2014), *consumer behavior* is strongly affected by cultural, social, personal and psychological factors. In which, *attitude* is one of the factors belonging to psychological characteristic which can affect consumer's *behavior*.

Figure 2.4 Factors Influencing Consumer Behavior by Kotler and Armstrong
 Source: Kotler & Armstrong (2014)

❖ **Davis (1989) – Technology Acceptance Model (TAM):**

TAM supposes that *behavioral intention* is an important factor that leads people to use a certain technology. According to David, the *behavioral intention* is also influenced by the *attitude* which is a factor determined by the *perceived usefulness* and *perceived ease of use* towards the technology.

Figure 2.5 Technology Acceptance Model (TAM)
 Source: David (1989)

❖ **Kim et al. (2009) – Extended valence framework (EVF):**

EVF is developed from the theoretical foundation of TRA (Ajzen, 1975) and TAM (Davis, 1989). EVF recognizes *trust* as a vital factor directly and indirectly affecting E-commerce *purchase intention*. The two mediators which are *risk* and *benefit* are affected by *trust* and have impacts on *purchase intention*. Particularly, *risk* has negative impact and *benefit* has positive impact on E-commerce *purchase intention*.

Figure 2.6 Extended valence framework (EVF)
 Source: Kim et al. (2009)

❖ **Some of other researches related BOPIS behavioral intention and their findings:**

Basically, there are many researches on behavioral intention developed based on the mentioned theories above. Although there are not really many studies specifically researching on BOPIS behavioral intention, the researches on related intentions towards choosing shopping channels like types of E-commerce shopping methods have been found, some of their findings are considered to be interesting and relevant to apply in this study:

In the studies related O2O (online to offline) commerce use intention, Yang et al. (2020), Chung & Nam (2020) or Lee (2017) indicated the core factors such as the *perceived benefit*, *perceived usefulness*, *perceived value* and the *perceived ease of use* have significant impacts on consumers' *attitude* and their O2O use *intention*. In which, Yang et al. (2020) clearly stated that the *benefit* has positive impacts on the *perceived value* and the

perceived usefulness which then have impact to the *attitude*. The *attitude* toward O2O usually roles as a *mediator* which highly determines the *intention* under the effects of other factors. The *perceived risk* is also considered in those studies, it however is not proved to significantly affect to consumers' *intention* in using O2O service, except from the research of Chung & Nam (2020).

The findings of particular studies on *BOPIS intention* are quite similar to the O2O ones but more specific. Chen & Chi (2020) researched on the intentions of U.S. consumers to use omnichannel shopping methods. The effects of channel integration of *promotion, product and price, transaction information, information access, order fulfillment, and customer service* were considered in the study under the mediating effects of the *perceived values, perceived risk, and perceived behavioral control*. The results showed that the *perceived values* and *perceived behavioral control* significantly impact to the consumers to select *buy online pickup in-store* (BOPIS) and *buy online curbside pickup* (BOCP). Kim *et al.* (2020) with the study about the effects of the antecedents of BOPIS service on consumer's BOPIS choice behavior identified that the *performance expectancy (perceived usefulness), trust, compatibility with BOPIS shopping, hedonic motivation and social influence* affect the behavioral intentions in choosing BOPIS. Meanwhile, Victor *et al.* (2018) found the *online trust* and *perceived usefulness* significantly affect the acceptance of *click and collect* e-tailing services among urban consumers. Nevertheless, *perceived risk* still is not demonstrated to have significant effect in those studies.

To e-grocery field, there is the study of Leo & Ellen (2021) which explained the intention to adopt or continue to use e-grocery services by the *perceived risk, perceived time pressure, perceived in-store shopping enjoyment, and innovativeness*. Dezie & Roozbeh (2022) indicated the factors driving the actual purchasing of groceries through E-commerce platforms which are *the ease of use, usefulness, attitude, and the reference group*. Kian *et al.* (2018) similarly found that the *perceived usefulness, perceived risk, visibility* and the *social influence* have impacts on the purchase intention of customers on online grocery shopping. Sarah (2017) supposed the *perceived internet grocery risk, perceived online shopping convenience, prior online shopping experience, and the grocery variety seeking* significantly impact on online grocery shopping intention. Martin & Radka (2020) clearly explained why retail customers hesitate for shopping grocery online that mainly because of the *preference to see grocery in person, the distrust e-merchants in choosing the best or freshest grocery, the habit of shopping in traditional stores* as well as the *hedonic shopping in traditional stores, time consumption, distrust in the easiness of return policy* along with the *unwillingness to pay for the delivery*.

In general, BOPIS is still a form of e-commerce as well as an ideal omnichannel retail strategy which integrates both online and offline features (Alexis Damen, 2022; Chen & Chi, 2021; Kim *et al.*, 2020), BOPIS is also considered as a subtype of O2O commerce model according to the classification of Shari *et al.* (2015). Therefore, the findings of the

above researches including the studies towards e-commerce or O2O commerce can be used as sources of reference for this study to develop the conceptual framework and hypotheses.

CHAPTER 3: HYPOTHESES DEVELOPMENT

3.1 PROPOSAL RESEARCH FRAMEWORK

By combining theories and findings of previous researches, the author of this study realizes that despite many effecting factors, the *attitude* and *behavioral intention* towards BOPIS for grocery purchase may be primarily influenced by the three main factors which are the *perceived benefit*, *perceived ease of use* and *perceived risk*. *Attitude* has a high probability to affect *behavioral intention* and roles as a mediator between *behavioral intention* and the other effecting factors. The impacts of the effecting factors on *behavioral intention* may also be influenced by moderators which could be consumer's *knowledge* and *experience with BOPIS*. In spite of no BOPIS researches related those moderators, they are considered in this study with the expectation to bring new interesting findings. The proposal framework is as the *figure 3.1* below, the hypotheses development with detailed explanations as well as reasons for all of the factors to be selected and the relationships to be investigated in this study are stated in the *section 3.2*.

Figure 3.1 The proposal framework

3.2 HYPOTHESIS DEVELOPMENT

(1) *Perceived benefit and Attitude*

Perceived Benefit (PB) refers to consumer subjective perceptions about the potential positive values from the transaction which they may gain, the benefits could be cost savings, time savings, convenience, vast product selections, and the ease of acquiring shopping information (Kim *et al.*, 2009), those benefits are likely to form the willingness to purchase online from consumers. The benefits of visiting a brick-and-mortar store compared to online shopping are the ambience, gratification, experience of touch and feel, etc., that keep consumers prefer brick-and-mortar stores (Misra *et al.*, 2017). BOPIS is integrated online and offline channel so it can take the benefits of both channels. Consumer perceived

benefits of click and collect created a long-term value in their perception (Jara *et al.*, 2018). The *benefit* has positive impacts not only on the *perceived value* but also the *perceived usefulness* which can affect to *attitude* of consumers (Yang *et al.*, 2020). This study considers *perceived benefit* as the factor directly effect to consumer *attitude* towards BOPIS for grocery purchase and believes there is a positive relationship between the two factors.

H1: *Perceived benefit* has a positive impact on consumer's *attitude* towards using BOPIS for grocery purchase.

(2) *Perceived risk and Attitude*

Perceived risk (PR) refers to a consumer's perception of the likely losses resulting from a transaction (Yang *et al.*, 2020; Kim *et al.*, 2009). Risks are the main concern of consumers when involving in any online shopping models which typically related to privacy, finance, product, performance, and even time, sociology or psychology (Sharma, 2017). *Perceived risk* negatively effects to e-grocery purchase intention (Sarah, 2017; Leo & Ellen, 2021; Kian *et al.*, 2021). On the other hand, consumer's intention to use a type of e-commerce which is integrated offline features as O2O is not significantly affected by perceived risks (Yang *et al.*, 2020; Chen & Chi, 2021; Lee, 2017; Victor *et al.*, 2018). However, the research of Chung & Nam (2020) still proved the negative significant effect of perceived risks on customer's attitudes and O2O use intention. This study believes that every new model contains potential risks and consumer's perceived risks towards BOPIS may make them hesitate to use the service for grocery purchase so it is likely to have a negative effect on consumer attitudes.

H2: *Perceived risk* has a negative impact on consumer's *attitude* towards using BOPIS for grocery purchase.

(3) *Perceived ease of use and Attitude*

Perceived ease of use (PE) refers to the degree to which a person believes that using a particular system would be free of effort (Davis, 1989) or would be easy to be understood, operated, and skillfully mastered (Yang *et al.*, 2020). It is the factor affecting consumer's attitude towards an innovation and leads to the intention of using that innovation. Since different models of E-commerce appear including e-grocery, the perceived eases of use determine whether or not consumers adopt them (Dezie & Roozbeh, 2022; Lee, 2017; Nam & Chung, 2020; Yang *et al.*, 2020). Nevertheless, purchasing with BOPIS requires both efforts of ordering items on the online system as pure online shopping and efforts of coming to the site to pick up the items in person. Therefore, the *ease of use* in this case is consumer's perception about the easiness when performing each stage in the whole process of BOPIS to purchase groceries. And, it is expected to have a positive impact on consumer's *attitude* towards BOPIS for grocery purchase.

H3: *Perceived ease of use* has a positive impact on consumer's *attitude* towards using BOPIS for grocery purchase.

(4) *Attitude and Behavioral intention*

All behavioral intentions derive from attitudes that is clearly stated in Theory of Reasoned Action (TRA) of Ajzen (1975) and has been verified by a large range of studies about consumer's behavioral intention (David, 1989; Chung & Nam, 2020; Lee, 2017; etc.). Also, the *attitude* is proved its mediating effect in the relationships of *behavioral intention* with other constructs in many models of those studies.

The *attitude* (AT) refers to the evaluation of an object, concept, or behavior along a dimension of favor or disfavor, good or bad, like or dislike (Ajzen, 2000), that is also consumer's subjective opinion and judgement (Yang *et al.*, 2000). Kotler & Armstrong (2014) similarly described *attitude* as a person's consistently favorable or unfavorable evaluations, feelings, and tendencies toward an object or idea. According to Mark & Hans (2004), the *attitude* can be measured in both utilitarian dimension (ex: useful, practical, efficient, etc.) and hedonic dimension (ex: fun, enjoyable, delightful, etc.). Meanwhile, the *behavioral intention* (BI) is an individual's readiness to perform a given behavior and it is based on the *attitude* towards that behavior (Ajzen, 2002). *Behavioral intention* towards BOPIS mentions about either the intention to use BOPIS or related behaviors might be performed by consumer in the future towards this omnichannel shopping method (Chen & Chi, 2021).

It is obvious that this study has adequate foundations to believe consumer's *attitude* is likely to affect the *behavioral intention* of consumers toward using BOPIS for grocery purchase and it contributes as a mediator in the framework. As a result, this is the fourth hypothesis of this study.

H4a: Consumer's *attitude* has a positive impact on consumer's *behavioral intention* towards using BOPIS for grocery purchase.

H4b: Consumer's *attitude* contributes as a mediating factor between *behavioral intention* and the other effecting factors.

(5) *BOPIS knowledge and BOPIS experience*

In addition to the main factors, this study also would like to investigate the moderating effects of *BOPIS knowledge* and *BOPIS experience*. Moderating factors in a model can change the strength, or even the direction of a relationship between two factors (Hair *et al.*, 2021) and this study have a strong belief that the above relationships are not simple but are likely to be affected by third factors. *Knowledge* and *experience* are proved to have moderator effects in some models related consumer's behavior (Wang *et al.*, 2016; Zhang, 2020; Liu *et al.*, 2022). Because moderators can be measured with a single item or multiple items (Hair *et al.*, 2021), this study simply measure knowledge and experience with single

questions to know whether the respondents have known or heard about BOPIS before, or even used to use BOPIS for their purchase in the past. The *BOPIS knowledge* and *BOPIS experience* are expected to impact on consumer *attitude* and *behavioral intention* towards using BOPIS for grocery purchase when there is at least one relationship among factors in the model influenced by them.

H5a: There is a moderating impact of *BOPIS knowledge* on relationships of the effecting factors with consumer's *attitude* and *behavioral intention* towards using BOPIS for grocery purchase.

H5b: There is a moderating impact of *BOPIS experience* on relationships of the effecting factors with consumer's *attitude* and *behavioral intention* towards using BOPIS for grocery purchase.

Table 3.1 Table of Hypotheses and investigated relationships

Hypotheses	Investigated relationships					
H1: <i>Perceived benefit</i> has a positive impact on consumer's <i>attitude</i> towards using BOPIS for grocery purchase.	PB → AT					
H2: <i>Perceived risk</i> has a negative impact on consumer's <i>attitude</i> towards using BOPIS for grocery purchase.	PR → AT					
H3: <i>Perceived ease of use</i> has a positive impact on consumer's <i>attitude</i> towards using BOPIS for grocery purchase.	PE → AT					
H4a: Consumer's <i>attitude</i> has a positive impact on consumer's <i>behavioral intention</i> towards using BOPIS for grocery purchase.	AT → BI					
H4b: Consumer's <i>attitude</i> contributes as a mediating factor between <i>behavioral intention</i> and the other factors.	<table style="border: none;"> <tr> <td style="border: none;">PB → BI</td> <td rowspan="3" style="border: none;">} under AT mediator</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="border: none;">PR → BI</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="border: none;">PR → BI</td> </tr> </table>	PB → BI	} under AT mediator	PR → BI	PR → BI	
PB → BI	} under AT mediator					
PR → BI						
PR → BI						
H5a: There is a moderating impact of <i>BOPIS knowledge</i> on relationships of the effecting factors with consumer's <i>attitude</i> and <i>behavioral intention</i> towards using BOPIS for grocery purchase..	<table style="border: none;"> <tr> <td style="border: none;">PB → AT</td> <td rowspan="4" style="border: none;">} under <i>BOPIS knowledge</i> moderator</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="border: none;">PR → AT</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="border: none;">PR → AT</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="border: none;">AT → BI</td> </tr> </table>	PB → AT	} under <i>BOPIS knowledge</i> moderator	PR → AT	PR → AT	AT → BI
PB → AT	} under <i>BOPIS knowledge</i> moderator					
PR → AT						
PR → AT						
AT → BI						
H5b: There is a moderating impact of <i>BOPIS experience</i> on relationships of the effecting factors with consumer's <i>attitude</i> and <i>behavioral intention</i> towards using BOPIS for grocery purchase.	<table style="border: none;"> <tr> <td style="border: none;">PB → AT</td> <td rowspan="4" style="border: none;">} under <i>BOPIS experience</i> moderator</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="border: none;">PR → AT</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="border: none;">PR → AT</td> </tr> <tr> <td style="border: none;">AT → BI</td> </tr> </table>	PB → AT	} under <i>BOPIS experience</i> moderator	PR → AT	PR → AT	AT → BI
PB → AT	} under <i>BOPIS experience</i> moderator					
PR → AT						
PR → AT						
AT → BI						

3.3 DESCRIPTION AND MEASUREMENT OF VARIABLES:

Together with the developed hypotheses, also based on the literature reviews, this part gives better understandings about all of the main variables in the framework by providing their final definitions and measuring them with particular items/observed variables which are used to ask respondents and analyzed in the following sections to figure out which one really contribute to the factors. The details and basis for each variable are as the *table 3.2* below:

Table 3.2 Description and measurement of variables

Variable	Definition	Items		Reference
		Questions	Referred to	
Perceived benefit (PB)	Consumers' perception of all the potential positive values that they can gain from using BOPIS	PB1. Shopping with BOPIS gives me advantage of online information	<i>Online information</i>	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2020)
		PB2. Shopping with BOPIS gives me advantage of offline physical experience	<i>Offline physical experience</i>	Kim <i>et al.</i> (2009)
		PB3. BOPIS provides me with greater flexibility than pure online grocery shopping. I can shop whenever I want and collect my orders at my convenience	<i>Flexibility</i>	
		PB4. BOPIS helps me save more time and effort in terms of searching, selecting products and waiting at the store compared to traditionally going physical shopping for grocery	<i>Time and effort saving</i>	
		PB5. BOPIS helps me save shipping fees	<i>Shipping fee saving</i>	
		PB6. It is easier for me to ask for changes or product returns and refunds than pure online shopping if I apply BOPIS	<i>Easy returns and refunds</i>	
		PB7. By using BOPIS, I am able to possess the product in its original condition right at the store without being affected by the delivery process	<i>Product original condition</i>	
Perceived Risk (PR)	Consumers' perception of the likely losses	PR1. My privacy information may easily be exposed to the use of BOPIS shopping.	<i>Privacy risk</i>	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2020)

Variable	Definition	Items		Reference
		Questions	Referred to	
	resulting from using BOPIS	PR2. Online payment may lead to the high potential of monetary losses such as from the exposure of checking account and passwords or being hacked by someone	<i>Financial risk</i>	Chung & Nam (2020) Victor <i>et al.</i> (2018)
		PR3. The online information (e.g: inventory, product descriptions, promotions, etc.) can be different from the reality at the store.	<i>Information risk</i>	
		PR4. The actual products of perishable groceries may be in low-quality or don't meet my expectations	<i>Product risk</i>	
		PR5. My order may not be fulfilled exactly and punctually when I come to collect it	<i>Performance risk</i>	
Perceived ease of use (PE)	Consumers' perception that using BOPIS service would be free of effort or easy to be understood, operated, and skillfully mastered.	PE1. The process of BOPIS is clear and understandable	<i>Clear and understandable process</i>	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2020)
		PE2. It is easy for me to use the online system to make orders	<i>Ease to use online system</i>	Kim <i>et al.</i> (2020)
		PE3. It is easy for me to learn using online system to make orders	<i>Ease to learn using online system</i>	Lee (2017)
		PE4. It is easy for me to access and pick up the product at the physical store.	<i>Ease to access the physical store</i>	
		PE5. The whole process of purchasing with BOPIS is simple to me	<i>Simple process</i>	Davis (1989)
		PE6. I can be mastered at shopping with BOPIS	<i>Ease to be mastered</i>	

Variable	Definition	Items		Reference
		Questions	Referred to	
Attitude towards BOPIS (AT)	Consumer's subjective opinion and judgement about BOPIS with grocery purchase	AT1. I feel that using BOPIS to shop for groceries is helpful	<i>Feel it helpful</i>	Marks & Hans (2004)
		AT2. I feel that using BOPIS to shop for groceries is enjoyable	<i>Feel it enjoyable</i>	
		AT3. I feel that using BOPIS to shop for groceries is practical	<i>Feel it practical</i>	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2020)
		AT4. I feel that using BOPIS to shop for groceries is efficient	<i>Feel it efficient</i>	Kotler & Armstrong (2014)
		AT5. I feel that using BOPIS to shop for groceries is a good idea	<i>Good idea</i>	
		AT6. I like the idea of using BOPIS to purchase groceries	<i>Like it</i>	
Behavioral Intention towards BOPIS (BI)	Consumer's willingness to use BOPIS to shop for groceries or behave towards it	BI1. I am willing to try using BOPIS to purchase groceries	<i>Intention to try</i>	Chen & Chi (2021)
		BI2. I think I would use BOPIS to purchase groceries in the future	<i>Intention to use</i>	
		BI3. I will encourage other people to use BOPIS service to purchase groceries if after using I find it really good	<i>Intention to encourage other people to use</i>	Kim <i>et al.</i> (2020)
		BI4. I maybe list BOPIS as one of my top options to purchase groceries in the future	<i>Intention to list it as a top option</i>	Yang <i>et al.</i> (2020)
		BI5. I will probably spread positive word of mouth about BOPIS to other people	<i>Intention to spread positive word of mouth</i>	

CHAPTER 4: METHODOLOGY

4.1 DATA ANALYSIS METHOD

4.1.1 Describe the data by Descriptive statistics

Descriptive statistics are to analyze, summarize, and present findings related to a data set with three main categories:

- *Frequency Distribution*
- *Measures of Central Tendency* (mean, median and mode)
- *Measures of Variability* (standard deviation S and variance S²).

This study uses descriptive statistics to describe general information of the collected observations such as gender, age, education level and many other variables to give better understanding about the sample, so that the equivalent population can be inferred. Descriptive statistics also gives the basis for further analysis of this study later.

4.1.2 Checking the differences among intentions of using BOPIS to purchase difference categories of grocery by using Paired samples T test

According to SPSS tutorials of Kent State University, *Paired samples T test* is used to test the mean difference between two measurements with the null hypothesis H₀: $\mu_1 = \mu_2$ (the means are equal) and the alternative hypothesis H: $\mu_1 \neq \mu_2$ (the means are not equal). The null hypothesis can be rejected if the p-value corresponding to the test with the degrees of freedom is less than 0.05.

This study uses *Paired samples T test* to simply check the mean difference in consensus levels for the use BOPIS to purchase three different categories of grocery products which measured by the question 7 in the questionnaire (*appendix 1*). From that, we are able to somewhat understand the consumer's intention towards using BOPIS for purchasing different categories of grocery.

4.1.3 Check reliability of the measurement by Cronbach's Alpha

Cronbach coefficient alpha (α) is the most popular scale test within the internal consistency method (Cronbach, 1951) with $\alpha = N\rho/[1+\rho(N-1)]$ (where ρ is the average correlation coefficient between the items in question; N is the number of items). Corrected Item-Total Correlation coefficient of each item must be greater than 0.3 and Cronbach's α coefficient should be greater than 0.7 (Hair *et al.*, 2006) or 0.6 (Nunnally, 1978) for the measure to be reliable.

By the use of Cronbach's Alpha, the proposal items in *section 3.3* can be checked for the reliability of measurement, only the qualified items are kept and used for factor analysis to find out the factors.

4.1.4 Structural Equation Model (SEM) to find out the factors and their relationships

Structural equation modeling (SEM) depicts the relations among the constructs (latent variables) and their items (observed variables) in various types of theoretical models, which provide a quantitative test of a hypothesis by the researcher (Randall & Richard, 2016). SEM includes two types which are the measurement model and the structural model. Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) and path analysis are used to investigate the relationships of all relevant variables in the two models (Fan *et al.*, 2016).

4.1.4.1 Confirmation Factor Analysis (CFA)

Confirmatory factor analysis (CFA) is used to measure latent variables or factors. CFA can be used to estimate the scale reliability and provide compelling evidence of the convergent and discriminant validity of theoretical constructs (Brown, 2015). CFA is a modern method of factor analysis. It is related to EFA but does not suffer from several of the limitations of EFA for bias research (Fontaine, 2005).

In factor analysis, principal components analysis (PCA) and principal axis factoring (PAF) are commonly used to extract factors which PCA is mostly used (Thompson, 2004). The factor loadings are the correlation coefficients between observed variables and latent factors, and are supposed 0.30 = minimal, 0.40 = important, and 0.50 = practically (Hair *et al.*, 2006). This study expects to have the significance in important level so the items with factor loadings < 0.4 will be eliminated. Besides, Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin (KMO) and Bartlett's Test must be considered to examine the adequacy of the sample and the suitability of data. KMO values must be greater than 0.5 (Kaiser, 1974) and Bartlett's test of Sphericity must be significant (p-value less than 0.05) to be acceptable for factor analysis (Hair *et al.*, 2006). The number of factors is determined based on the retention of factors which the Kaiser's eigenvalue > 1 (Hooper, 2012). In addition, the cumulative total variance explained which gives the percentage of variance accounted for by the first n components should greater than 60% (Hair *et al.*, 2006).

Other indicators which determine the construct validity of measurement model are the Average Variance Extracted (AVE) and Construct Reliability (CR). The AVE > 0.5 and CR > 0.7 where the CR > AVE are required for the convergent validity. Also, the AVE values of each latent construct > MSV (the corresponding maximum shared variance) or ASV (the average shared variance) values when the $\sqrt{AVE} >$ all correlation coefficients of the variable with others, are required for the discriminant validity. (Hair *et al.*, 2014; Fornell & Larcker, 1981)

In general, using the CFA is to find out all the factors along with their observed variables and confirm both the reliability and validity of them. After that the reliable and valid items are used in the structural model for further analysis.

4.1.4.2 Investigate the relationships among factors by path analysis

Path analysis explains the causal relationships among variables. According to David (2005), path analysis is an extension of multiple regression which allows for the analysis of more complicated models.

This study conducts the multivariate analysis which considers the effects of factors on the behavioral intention of Vietnamese consumers toward BOPIS for grocery purchase and their attitude is the mediator. Thus, using path analysis is critical and necessary in this case to comprehensively find out all the relationships among the variables on each path of the structural model.

4.1.4.3 Test mediating effect in SEM by using bootstrapping

According to Baron and Kenny (1986) the principle of testing a mediating effect is: (1) *checking the indirect effect* of the independent variable (IV) on the dependent variable (DV) under the influence of a mediator (Me) ($IV \rightarrow Me$ and $Me \rightarrow DV$). If X significantly has an indirect effect on DV which means IV significantly affects to Me and Me significantly affects to DV, then this demonstrates the mediating effect of Me. (2) To get to know whether Me effects partially or fully on the relationship of IV and DV, it is necessary to *check the direct effect* of $IV \rightarrow DV$ under Me influence. If IV still significantly affects to DV, it means Me just has a partial effect. But if no effect of IV on DV is found, it means Me fully effects on the relationship of IV and DV. The effect of a mediator can be investigated by step by step conducting regression on each relationship mentioned above. It either can be analyzed by using the PROCESS macro developed by Hayes. However, using Amos to run bootstrapping on SEM is supposed to as a better way.

Bootstrapping is used for examining the indirect effect with the null hypothesis H_0 of no indirect effect is not supported at, for instance, $\alpha = 0.05$ if zero is not included in the lower and upper bounds of the 95% confidence interval (Harsha, 2013). This method can be simply performed on SEM in the Amos software.

Similarly, if the structural model is successfully built based on the proposal framework, this study will use this method to check the mediating effect of the attitude (AT) on the relationships of the behavioral intention (BI) with other effecting factors (PB, PR and PE) at the confidential level of 95%.

4.1.4.4 Test moderation in SEM by using Multigroup Analysis

There are commonly two types of moderator which are categorical and continuous. According to Newsom (2020), Multigroup analysis can be used to investigate the mediation when the moderator is a categorical variable. The relationship of variables in a structural equation modeling could be tested in separated groups. The equality constraints could then be imposed and the chi-square for the equality constrained model would then be compared to the chi-square for the model in which the path(s) were estimated separately and freely

in the separated groups (unconstrained) (Newsom, 2020). For the test to be significant, the difference in Chi-Square value of constrained model and unconstrained model must be more than 3.84, then the moderation occurs in that path (Awang, 2012).

Actually, there are several ways to test moderation including manually conducting a regression analysis with the interaction term (IV x Mo) or using Process Macro in SPSS. However, because *BOPIS knowledge* and *BOPIS experience* are categorical variables, Multigroup analysis on SEM can be applied. Moreover, this method can be easily conducted in Amos.

4.1.4.5 SEM evaluation indices

Any model built up should be checked for the Goodness-of-Fit to make sure it is a good model and suitable for analysis. There are a huge variety of indices to test the significance and measure the Goodness-of-Fit in SEM. This study considers the typical indices applied by Liu *et al.* (2019) as standards for a fit model:

Table 4.1 Standards for the fit of model

Indices	Statistical test	Standard
Absolute goodness of fit	χ^2/df or CMIN/DF	$3 \leq \text{CMIN/DF} \leq 5$ as acceptable range $\text{CMIN/DF} \leq 3$ model fitting degree is excellent
	RMSEA (estimated root mean square)	$0.05 \leq \text{RMSEA} \leq 0.1$ as acceptable range $\text{RMSEA} < 0.05$ Height fitting model
Relative fitting index	NFI (normal fit index)	$\text{NFI} > 0.8$, as acceptable range; $\text{NFI} > 0.9$, model fitting degree is good
	IFI (incremental fit index)	$\text{IFI} > 0.8$, as acceptable range; $\text{IFI} > 0.9$, model fitting degree is good
	CFI (comparative fit index)	$\text{CFI} > 0.8$, as acceptable range; $\text{CFI} > 0.9$, model fitting degree is good
Simplified goodness of fit index	PGFI (simplified fit index)	$\text{PGFI} > 0.5$, as acceptable range; Closer to 1, the better the model fits

Source: Liu *et al.* (2019)

4.2 DATA ANALYSIS TOOLS

To achieve the research aims by the selected methods for data analysis, this study uses two main types statistical software which are IBM SPSS Statistics 20 and IBM Amos 20. Those two types of software are reliable and widely used in scientific research field for data analysis because of its high accuracy and ease of use. They are believed to have the sufficient functions to support for all analyses in this research.

4.3 DATA COLLECTION METHOD

4.3.1 Sample size

For structural equation model (SEM), the size of sample is critical because it can affect the parameter estimate and the model fit result. There are various rules of thumb and guidelines offered by scholars for ideal sample sizes in SEM. Kline (2005) considered sample of 100 is small, 100 to 200 is medium, and a sample over 200 is large. The sample size is also commonly determined by the ratio of N:q in SEM analysis. And, Bentler & Chou (1987) just supposed 5 cases per parameter is a minimum size in SEM analysis. This study researches on 29 questions/items so the minimum sample size should be $5 \times 29 = 145$ observations. However, 200 observations are this study's data collecting target to have a better sample as the standard of Kline (2005).

4.3.2 Measurement scales

This study basically builds up the questionnaire based on nominal and ordinal scales. Although the 5 and 7 point scales are both usually applied in studies using SEM, Montri (2020) stated that the higher the Likert point scale, the better it could control the type I error and the higher the power of the test on both parametric and nonparametric tests. And, the measurement scales are better in 7-point Likert scale (Bollen 1989). Therefore, the 7 - point likert scale is applied in this research with 1 = "Strongly disagree"; 2 = "Disagree"; 3 = "Somewhat disagree"; 4 = "Neutral"; 5 = "Somewhat agree"; 6 = "Agree"; and 7 = "Strongly Agree". The questionnaire is attached in the appendix 1.

4.3.3 Sampling method

Due to distance and funding constrains, this study applies non-probability sampling method in a convenient way randomly collecting data from Vietnamese consumers by running an online survey. The link accessing to the survey is published online on the popular social networks in Vietnam (such as Facebook, Zalo or Instagram) to easily and cheaply approach to prospective respondents.

CHAPTER 5: ANALYSIS AND DISCUSSION

5.1 UNDERSTANDING OF THE SAMPLE

Because of the limitation of an online survey from a far distance, in order to reach the initial target of 200 observations, the survey had to last more than two months. Finally, there were 203 respondents whose answers are eligible to be used in this study. The outputs of descriptive statistic for all questions are stated in *appendix 2 section 1*. Except from the question 5a which is an opening question (*appendix 1*), the other questions are fully answered by respondents without any missing answer. The general description of the data is described as followings:

Table 5.1 The general description of data

Questions	n	Type of variable	Missing	Frequency of answers							Mean	Std. Deviation	
				1	2	3	4	5	6	7			
Q1	203	Ordinal	0	18	23	65	97						
Q2	203	Nominal	0	140	63								
Q3	203	Nominal	0	21	74	69	32	7					
Q4	203	Nominal	0	161	42								
Q5	203	Nominal	0	78	125								
Q6	203	Ordinal	0	11	59	80	36	17					
Q7	a	203	Interval	0	11	11	11	35	21	75	39	5.09	1.699
	b	203	Interval	0	14	23	23	47	35	43	18	4.32	1.709
	c	203	Interval	0	10	9	11	29	25	74	45	5.23	1.661
Q8	PB1	203	Interval	0	11	8	14	29	33	80	28	5.05	1.611
	PB2	203	Interval	0	17	20	20	31	40	53	22	4.50	1.798
	PB3	203	Interval	0	16	9	18	23	23	74	40	5.02	1.816
	PB4	203	Interval	0	18	9	13	18	20	76	49	5.15	1.870
	PB5	203	Interval	0	19	14	19	26	29	60	36	4.75	1.893
	PB6	203	Interval	0	18	15	15	33	21	69	32	4.77	1.864
	PB7	203	Interval	0	20	5	17	21	24	70	46	5.06	1.871
	PR1	203	Interval	0	14	12	25	48	32	57	15	4.49	1.642
	PR2	203	Interval	0	17	21	19	31	35	60	20	4.51	1.806
	PR3	203	Interval	0	16	15	16	36	38	58	24	4.65	1.752
	PR4	203	Interval	0	14	12	16	26	35	65	35	4.93	1.760
	PR5	203	Interval	0	14	15	14	31	43	61	25	4.76	1.717
	PE1	203	Interval	0	12	3	12	45	41	72	18	4.91	1.500
	PE2	203	Interval	0	12	9	7	40	35	75	25	4.98	1.598
	PE3	203	Interval	0	13	5	12	26	39	75	33	5.12	1.622
PE4	203	Interval	0	13	7	12	33	37	79	22	4.97	1.603	
PE5	203	Interval	0	14	8	12	42	29	73	25	4.89	1.660	
PE6	203	Interval	0	11	7	8	35	39	71	32	5.09	1.578	

Questions	n	Type of variable	Missing	Frequency of answers							Mean	Std. Deviation
				1	2	3	4	5	6	7		
AT1	203	Interval	0	9	9	8	49	30	70	28	4.99	1.554
AT2	203	Interval	0	11	13	10	50	35	60	24	4.78	1.618
AT3	203	Interval	0	11	12	15	34	36	66	29	4.90	1.662
AT4	203	Interval	0	9	11	16	44	40	60	23	4.81	1.566
AT5	203	Interval	0	11	10	8	36	31	72	35	5.08	1.642
AT6	203	Interval	0	9	10	14	38	31	71	30	5.00	1.603
BI1	203	Interval	0	11	9	12	37	36	67	31	4.99	1.624
BI2	203	Interval	0	12	9	12	36	36	65	33	4.98	1.656
BI3	203	Interval	0	13	8	10	40	31	64	37	5.01	1.683
BI4	203	Interval	0	12	13	20	40	36	62	20	4.68	1.650
BI5	203	Interval	0	12	9	13	43	41	62	23	4.82	1.598
Q9	203	Ordinal	0	18	168	17						
Q10	203	Nominal	0	74	128	1						
Q11	203	Nominal	0	158	16	29						
Q12	203	Ordinal	0	27	121	55						
Q13	203	Ordinal	0	78	98	27						

5.1.1 General information

✓ **Age:** In 203 observations, there are 3 groups of age in which 18 observations (8.87 %) are under 22 years old, 168 observations (82.76 %) are from 22 to 34 years old, and 17 observations (8.37 %) are 35 years old or older. As the result, majority of the sample is in the age of 22 to 34. Due to this reason, maybe this study is only able to reflect accurately on this group of consumers.

✓ **Gender:** 128 observations (63.05%) are female, 74 observations (36.45%) are male and 1 observation (0.49%) supposes that he/she is of another sex. The data shows the percentage of female is higher male, this is quite reasonable because the female more usually go shopping for groceries than male in reality. The study wants to go further to research even on other special genders, however they survey did not reach this group of respondents so there is only one respondent of other gender, it is just a minority so it will not be considered in this study.

✓ **Marital status:** There are 158 observations are single (77.83%), 16 observations have been married without children (7.88%), and 29 observations have been married and had children already (14.29%). The survey approached respondents who are in young age so it leads to an equivalent result that most of them still be single.

✓ **Education level:** There are 27 observations have less than high school/ high school diploma (13.30%), 121 observations have college/bachelor's degree (59.61%), and 55 observations have postgraduate degree (27.09%). Although the sample has respondents

who just have less than high school or high school diplomas, they just count for a small percentage, most of the respondents still have high educational levels.

✓ **Income level:** Most of observations in the sample have low and average income. Specifically, there are 78 observations have monthly salary of under 8.000.000 VND (38.42%), 98 observations have monthly salary of 8.000.000 – under 20.000.000 VND (48.28%), and only 27 observations can earn 20.000.000 VND or more per month (13.30%) (where 1.000.000 VND is approximately 43 USD).

Table 5.2 General information of the sample

Characteristics		Frequency	Percent (%)	Cumulative Percent (%)
Groups of age	≥ 35 years old	17	8.37	8.37
	< 22 years old	18	8.87	17.24
	22 – 34 years old	168	82.76	100
	Total	203	100	
Gender	Female	128	63.05	63.05
	Male	74	36.45	99.51
	Others	1	0.49	100
	Total	203	100	
Marital status	Married, have children	29	14.29	14.29
	Married, no children	16	7.88	22.17
	Single	158	77.83	100
	Total	203	100	
Education level	College/ Bachelor’s Degree	121	59.61	59.61
	Less Than High School / High School Diploma	27	13.3	72.91
	Postgraduate Degree	55	27.09	100
	Total	203	100	
Income level	≥ 20.000.000 VND	27	13.3	13.3
	< 8.000.000 VND	78	38.42	51.72
	8.000.000 – under 20.000.000 VND	98	48.28	100
	Total	203	100	

From all those statistical results, it can be summarized that the sample of this study may not represent for the whole population which is Vietnamese consumers in general but it can well represent for the young generation whom many of them are still single and have low or mediate level of income. As the result, the subsequent analyzes in this study more accurately reflect to this group of consumers.

5.1.2 Grocery shopping habit

When being asked about grocery shopping frequency, 97 respondents (47.78%) say that they shop for groceries more than four times a month, 65 respondents (32.02%) say that they shop for groceries three – four times a month, 23 respondents (11.33%) purchase twice a month and 18 respondents (8.7%) purchase once a month for groceries. That means the observations in this sample are consumers who frequently purchase groceries or at least they have the experience shopping for groceries.

Table 5.3 Frequency that consumers go grocery shopping

How often do you go shopping for groceries?	Frequency	Percent (%)	Cumulative Percent (%)
Three - four times a month	65	32.02	32.02
More than four times a month	97	47.78	79.80
Once a month	18	8.87	88.67
Twice a month	23	11.33	100
Total	203	100	

In those observations, there are 140 respondents (68.97%) used to purchase groceries online and the remain 63 respondents (31.03%) have never purchased groceries online.

Table 5.4 Online grocery shopping experience

Have you ever purchased groceries online?	Frequency	Percent (%)	Cumulative Percent (%)
No	63	31.03	31.03
Yes	140	68.97	100
Total	203	100	

It can be inferred from the *table 5.3* and *table 5.4* that nowadays Vietnamese consumers all go grocery shopping and have their own grocery shopping experiences, especially since E-commerce development, many of them have engaged in online shopping for groceries.

However, most of consumers nowadays prefer to shop for groceries in hypermarkets (E.g: Go!, Lotte Mart, AEON, and Co.op Xtra) or supermarket and minimart (E.g: Bach Hoa Xanh, Vinmart), the number of respondents choosing retailers of those two shopping channels is 74 respondents and 69 respondents, respectively accounting for 36.45% and 33.99%. Their other choices are traditional groceries stores and local markets with 32 respondents (15.75%) who like to shop at traditional groceries stores and 21 respondents (10.34%) who like to shop at local markets. Surprisingly, there are only 7 respondents (3.45%) who prefer going online shopping for groceries.

Table 5.5 Priority channel for grocery shopping

If you are going to buy groceries which place you prioritize to go?	Frequency	Percent (%)	Cumulative Percent (%)
Hypermarket (E.g: Go!, Lotte Mart, AEON, and Co.op Xtra)	74	36.45	36.45
Local Market	21	10.34	46.80
Online stores	7	3.45	50.25
Supermarket and Minimarket (E.g: Bach Hoa Xanh, Vinmart)	69	33.99	84.24
Traditional Grocery Stores	32	15.76	100
Total	203	100	

The *table 5.5* primarily state that after all the online shopping is not consumers' priority choice, grocery shopping at hypermarkets or supermarkets are still their first preference. This maybe stem from some of the reasons mentioned in previous researches (Martin & Radka, 2020; Kian *et al.*, 2018; Sarah, 2017; Leo & Ellen, 2021). And, this is also quite similar to what this study's author raised in *chapter 1* that in this E-commerce era the traditional channels are still dominant in Vietnam. Therefore, there is a need for a better model of grocery retailing to solve the problems of pure online shopping but still take its advantages, BOPIS could be a potential option.

5.1.3 BOPIS knowledge and experience

The *table 5.6* below shows that the sample includes 161 observations (79.31%) are people who at least know or hear about BOPIS service and the rest of 42 observations (20.69%) who have never known about BOPIS. For those who know about the service, there are 78 observations (38.42%) who used to use BOPIS to buy something. When being asked further about what are the things they purchase by BOPIS, the typical answers from consumers are mobile phone, electronic devices, home appliances, food, clothes and surprisingly some say that they used to make grocery purchase by BOPIS. Although BOPIS for grocery purchase has not been widely applied in Vietnam, some people had a chance to experience the service, it is maybe when they were oversea or because there are some Vietnamese retailers have already started to offer the service to customers.

Table 5.6 BOPIS knowledge and experience

Answers	Have you ever known or heard about BOPIS?		Have you ever used BOPIS?	
	Frequency	Percent (%)	Frequency	Percent (%)
Yes	161	79.31	78	38.42
No	42	20.69	125	61.58
Total	203	100	203	100

Anyway, this statistical data about consumers' *BOPIS knowledge and experience* implies that the BOPIS service is not really new in Vietnam because currently there are certain amount of people have known or heard about it. However, it has not widely approached to the consumers, some consumers have BOPIS experiences but those consumers are not assumed to make up a very large portion. Thus, BOPIS for groceries is just in its very early dates and it needs more time to be well adopted and applied widely in Vietnam.

With a certain level of knowledge and experience about BOPIS, consumers have their own perception and evaluation about the service so that they can give better objective assessments about it. So that, the *BOPIS knowledge* and *BOPIS experience* are believed to lead to different attitudes and behavioral intentions of consumers towards the service as what proposed in *chapter 3*. The *section 5.2.2.3* would give better understandings about the effects of those two factors.

5.1.4 BOPIS intention for grocery purchase

5.1.4.1 Probability that consumers use BOPIS to purchase groceries

The *table 5.7* shows that most of respondents have BOPIS intention for grocery purchase at a certain level although there are still some of them who don't have any intention to use this kind of service (11 observations accounting for 5.42%). However, their intention to use BOPIS for grocery purchase is not really high since most of them have intention under 50%, 59 respondents (29.06%) say that the probability for them to purchase groceries with BOPIS is above 0% - 25% and 80 respondents (39.41%) say that the probability for them to purchase groceries with BOPIS is just above 25%-50%. As the result, totally 73.89% of respondents say that they will use BOPIS to purchase groceries but with the probability of only 50% or less. On the other hand, 36 observations (17.73%) have intention at probability of above 50%-75% and only 17 observations (5.37%) have intention to use the service for grocery purchase more than 75%.

Table 5.7 Probability that consumers use BOPIS to purchase groceries

What is the probability that you will use BOPIS service for grocery purchase?	Frequency	Percent (%)	Cumulative Percent
0%	11	5.42	5.42
Above 0% - 25%	59	29.06	34.48
Above 25% - 50%	80	39.41	73.89
Above 50% - 75%	36	17.73	91.63
Above 75% - 100%	17	8.37	100
Total	203	100	

5.1.4.2 Purchase intention based on product categories/characteristics

Suppose the consensus level of consumers is from 1 to 7 representing from “strongly disagree” to “strongly agree”. Descriptive statistics of the consensus levels of using BOPIS to purchase three main different categories of grocery are in the following table and figures:

Table 5.8 The consensus level of using BOPIS to purchase different grocery categories

Product categories/characteristics	n	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
a. Packaged food products which don't need to be temperature-controlled (E.g: instant noodles, canned fish, cookies, candy, ...)	203	1	7	5.09	1.699
b. Fresh and refrigerated food products which need to be temperature-controlled (E.g: dairy, raw meat, vegetables, ice cream, ...)	203	1	7	4.32	1.709
c. Non-food products (E.g: paper towels, shampoo, detergent, baby care items, ...)	203	1	7	5.23	1.661

Figure 5.1 Distribution of consumers' consensus level on using BOPIS to purchase packaged food product

Figure 5.2 Distribution of consumers' consensus level on using BOPIS to purchase fresh and refrigerated food product

Figure 5.3 Distribution of consumers' consensus level on using BOPIS to purchase non-food product

The above statistics show that in average the intention of using BOPIS to purchase products of the category b < the category a < the category c, the distribution of consumers' consensus level on using BOPIS to purchase the category b (fresh and refrigerated food products) looks different from the two other categories of grocery. That raises a question is whether the consensus levels for the use of BOPIS are really different among categories of grocery products.

The *Paired - samples T test* is conducted to check again the mean difference of those consensus levels to confirm whether the grocery category has significant effect in this case. Then, the result (*appendix 2 section 2*) stated in *table 5.9* indicates that there is a difference in consensus level for the use of BOPIS to purchase the category b (fresh/refrigerated food products) with the category a (packaged food products) and the category c (non-food products) (sig. < 0.05). Meanwhile, there is no significant difference in consensus level for the use of BOPIS to purchase the category a (packaged food products) and the category c (non-food products). Or, it can be implied that the intention using BOPIS to purchase fresh/refrigerated products is lower than the intention using BOPIS to purchase the other categories of grocery products at the confident interval of 95%.

Table 5.9 Paired differences of the consensus level of using BOPIS to purchase a particular category of grocery products with the other one.

		Paired Differences					t	df	P-value
		Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
					Lower	Upper			
Pair 1	a - b	0.778	1.792	0.126	0.530	1.026	6.187	202	0.000
Pair 2	a - c	-0.133	1.155	0.081	-0.293	0.027	-1.641	202	0.102
Pair 3	b - c	-0.911	1.738	0.122	-1.152	-0.671	-7.469	202	0.000

In general, this section specifies that Vietnamese consumers have a certain level of intention to use BOPIS for their grocery purchase in future but it not really high because 73.89% of consumers will use the service with the probability of only 50% or less (*table 5.7*). Especially, consumers seem have less intention of using BOPIS to purchase for the fresh and refrigerated food products which need to be temperature-controlled, compared to the packaged food products which do not need to be temperature-controlled and the non-food products (*table 5.8* and *table 5.9*). This is quite understandable because the fresh and refrigerated food products may be sensitive or not homogeneous, consumers obviously concern about the quality of products selected by other people. This is either one of the reasons make consumers hesitate to shop grocery online mentioned by Martin & Radka (2020). This problem is not only of pure online shopping but also of BOPIS since consumers are not able to see and select the real items by themselves at the beginning. Thus, it is inferred that ensuring the quality and the homogeneity of the products is important to enhance consumers' purchase intention with BOPIS service.

5.2 FACTORS AFFECTING CONSUMER ATTITUDE AND BEHAVIORAL INTENTION TOWARDS BOPIS FOR GROCERY PURCHASE

5.2.1 Confirmation factor analysis (CFA)

✓ Checking the reliability by Cronbach's alpha

After running Cronbach's alpha with the data of the proposal measurement items, the result of table 5.10 (summarized from the outputs of *appendix 2 section 3*) shows that all the Cronbach's alpha coefficients of factors are greater than 0.7 and the Corrected Item-Total Correlation coefficient of each item is greater than 0.3 so the measurement scales of factors are supposed to be reliable for factor analysis and no items need to be deleted from the measurement.

Table 5.10 The result of Cronbach's Alpha

Factors	Items	Cronbach's Alpha	n of Items	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
PB	PB1	0.931	7	0.769	0.922
	PB2			0.670	0.931
	PB3			0.816	0.917
	PB4			0.814	0.917
	PB5			0.783	0.920
	PB6			0.784	0.920
	PB7			0.823	0.916
PR	PR1	0.928	5	0.731	0.927
	PR2			0.828	0.909
	PR3			0.828	0.909
	PR4			0.821	0.910
	PR5			0.849	0.905
PE	PE1	0.961	6	0.883	0.953
	PE2			0.870	0.954
	PE3			0.872	0.954
	PE4			0.893	0.952
	PE5			0.865	0.955
	PE6			0.879	0.953
AT	AT1	0.967	6	0.874	0.963
	AT2			0.863	0.964
	AT3			0.872	0.964
	AT4			0.919	0.959
	AT5			0.928	0.958
	AT6			0.911	0.959
BI	BI1	0.964	5	0.883	0.957
	BI2			0.919	0.952
	BI3			0.898	0.955
	BI4			0.884	0.957
	BI5			0.901	0.955

✓ Factor analysis:

After checking the reliability by Cronbach Alpha, none of them were excluded, the factor analysis is conducted with 29 observed variables. The result of factor analysis (*appendix 2 section 4.1*) shows the KMO = 0.947 is closer to 1.0 so it is considered ideal. Bartlett's Test of Sphericity has sig. = 0.000 (<0.05) means this factor analysis is suitable. The result remains all of the 29 observed variables (factor loadings > 0.4) and contribute

to 5 components which have Eigenvalues > 1. The cumulative total variance explained of 81.402 % is the percentage of variance accounted for by those 5 components which is considered good (> 60%). In general, this factor analysis result is ideally similar to the original proposal of the author.

Table 5.11 The result of Rotated Component Matrix

	Component				
	1	2	3	4	5
PB1	0.704				
PB2	0.684				
PB3	0.694				
PB4	0.723				
PB5	0.765				
PB6	0.781				
PB7	0.774				
PR1					0.809
PR2					0.883
PR3					0.841
PR4					0.834
PR5					0.855
PE1		0.768			
PE2		0.772			
PE3		0.775			
PE4		0.798			
PE5		0.725			
PE6		0.773			
AT1			0.748		
AT2			0.791		
AT3			0.751		
AT4			0.785		
AT5			0.775		
AT6			0.760		
BI1				0.733	
BI2				0.776	
BI3				0.752	
BI4				0.775	
BI5				0.792	

Figure 5.4 Scree plot and Eigenvalue of factor analysis

✓ The measurement model:

The measurement model of 5 factors measured by 29 items which is from the above result of factor analysis, needs to be checked for the Goodness-of-Fit before further analysis. In order to improve the model fitness, every pair of items which have high MI (Modification Indices) (*appendix 2 section 4.2*) were connected to each other by drawing covariances (e28 and e29, e6 and e7). Then, the final measurement model is as *figure 5.5* below which all of its critical indices meet the requirements (*section 4.1.4.5*) for the suitable measurement of all items and can be used for further analysis. Specifically, the Chi-square/df = 2.027 is lower than 3 demonstrating a perfect fit model, the RMSEA = 0.71 ($0.05 \leq RMSEA \leq 0.1$) is in an acceptable range. The NFI = 0.898 which is lower than 0.9 but it is still close to 0.9, the IFI = 0.946 and CFI = 0.946 (all greater than 0.9) represent a good fitting degree. The PGFI = 0.668 still ensures an acceptable fitting. This measurement model finally is a good fit model.

Figure 5.5 The measurement model of CFA

According to this measurement, all of factors are clearly defined by the respective observed variables proposed in *section 3.3*:

- The consumer attitudes (AT) towards BOPIS for grocery purchase now are verified to be related to consumer opinion and judgement about whether the BOPIS is *helpful* (AT1), *enjoyable* (AT2), *practical* (AT3), *efficient* (AT4) or whether it is a *good idea*

(AT5) and consumers like this idea (AT6) for their grocery purchase, as the contribution of 6 ATs in the proposal model.

- The consumer behavioral intentions (BI) consist of 5 main types of intention including the *intention to try (BI1)*, *intention to use (BI2)*, *intention to encourage other people to use (BI3)*, *intention to list BOPIS as a top option (BI4)* to purchase groceries and *the intention to spread positive word of mouth (BI5)* about the service to other people.
- The perceived benefits (PB) are confirmed to comprise 7 benefits which are the benefit of *online information (PB1)*, *offline physical experience (PB2)*, *flexibility (PB3)*, *time and effort saving (PB4)*, *shipping fee saving (PB5)*, *easy returns and refunds (PB6)*, and the *product original condition (PB7)*.
- The perceived risks (PR) are indicated to be related to 5 main types of risk as the proposal inclusive of the *privacy risk (PR1)*, *financial risk (PR2)*, *information risk (PR3)*, *product risk (PR4)*, and *performance risk (PR5)*.
- The perceived ease of use (PE) is measured by 6 dimensions including the *clear and understandable process (PE1)*, *ease to use online system (PE2)*, *ease to learn using online system (PE3)*, *ease to access the physical store (PE4)*, *simple process (PE5)*, and the *ease to be mastered (PE6)* with shopping with BOPIS.

✓ Test reliability and validity in CFA:

The above measurement is last confirmed by considering the standards for reliability and validity mentioned in *section 4.1.4.1*. The outputs from *appendix 2 section 3 and section 4* are used to create estimates of reliability and validity coefficients (*table 5.12*). The necessary requirements (*section 4.1.4.1*) are qualified to conclude that all items are reliable and valid to define the factors, specifically:

- As a result of factor analysis, all the factors' Cronbach's alpha coefficients are greater than 0.7, the factor loading of an item to its belonged factor is > 0.4 and to the other factors < 0.4 with none of items appear in more than two factors (*table 5.10 and table 5.11*). Moreover, the convergent validity (CR) coefficients of factors are greater than 0.7 and the average variance extracted (AVE) coefficients are greater than 0.5 which $CR > AVE$ implies not only the good reliability but also the convergent validity of the model (*table 5.12*).
- At the same time, *table 5.12* also shows that the values of AVE are greater the corresponding values of MSV (maximum shared variance) as well as each factor's \sqrt{AVE} (in *table 5.12* respectively 0.912; 0.806; 0.849; 0.898 and 0.911) is greater than all correlation coefficients of its with others, this is a strong evidence of the discriminant reliability.

After the whole process of CFA, all of the factors and their contributed variables are determined and verified. This is also the foundation to build up the structural model and investigate the relationship among factors in the following section.

Table 5.12 The estimates to check reliability and validity of measurement

Factors	Items	α	Factor loadings	CR	AVE	MSV	AT	PB	PR	PE	BI
AT:	AT1	0.97	0.748	0.967	0.832	0.594	$\sqrt{\text{AVE}}$ = 0.912				
	AT2		0.791								
	AT3		0.751								
	AT4		0.785								
	AT5		0.775								
	AT6		0.76								
PB:	PB1	0.93	0.704	0.928	0.649	0.507	0.712	$\sqrt{\text{AVE}}$ = 0.806			
	PB2		0.684								
	PB3		0.694								
	PB4		0.723								
	PB5		0.765								
	PB6		0.781								
	PB7		0.774								
PR:	PR1	0.93	0.809	0.928	0.721	0.260	0.402	0.51	$\sqrt{\text{AVE}}$ = 0.849		
	PR2		0.883								
	PR3		0.841								
	PR4		0.834								
	PR5		0.855								
PE:	PE1	0.96	0.768	0.962	0.806	0.591	0.743	0.71	0.392	$\sqrt{\text{AVE}}$ = 0.898	
	PE2		0.772								
	PE3		0.775								
	PE4		0.798								
	PE5		0.725								
	PE6		0.773								
BI:	BI1	0.96	0.733	0.961	0.830	0.594	0.771	0.69	0.389	0.769	$\sqrt{\text{AVE}}$ = 0.911
	BI2		0.776								
	BI3		0.752								
	BI4		0.775								
	BI5		0.792								

5.2.2 Investigate the effects of factors on consumer attitude and behavioral intention

5.2.2.1 The causal relationships among factors

The causal model is built based on the proposal framework with the confirmed factors measured by the above analysis. The data outputs are as *appendix 2 section 5*. It first is verified to be a good fitness model (*figure 5.6*) with the Chi-square/df = 2.125, the RMSEA = 0.75, the NFI = 0.893, the IFI = 0.940, the CFI = 0.940 and the PGFI = 0.668 (all of those values meet the requirements mentioned in the *section 4.1.4.5*). The path analysis along with the regression weights from the causal model demonstrates the relationships among variables (*figure 4.6* and *table 5.13*). The proposed hypotheses are investigated at the confidence level of 95% with the consideration of covariance relationships among latent factors (*table 5.14*).

Figure 5.6 The causal model of research

Table 5.13 Regression Weights of the causal model

	Estimate	Standardized Estimates	S.E.	p
PB → AT	0.369	0.357	0.081	***
PR → AT	0.037	0.033	0.062	0.557
PE → AT	0.491	0.487	0.073	***
AT → BI	0.860	0.781	0.065	***

Table 5.14 Covariances among variables

			Estimate	S.E.	p
PB	<-->	PR	0.818	0.149	***
PB	<-->	PE	1.271	0.175	***
PR	<-->	PE	0.643	0.138	***
e28	<-->	e29	0.357	0.060	***
e6	<-->	e7	0.691	0.125	***

The result (figure 5.6 and table 5.13) indicates the strong positive impact of the attitude (AT) on behavioral intention (BI) towards BOPIS for grocery purchase when the attitude (AT) is verified to be positively affected by consumer's perceived benefit (PB) and perceived ease of use (PE). The perceived risk (PR) however does not have a significant effect on the attitude (AT) in this model with the confidence interval of 95%.

- The hypothesis H1 is proved to be true, the *perceived benefit* has a positive impact on the consumer's attitude towards BOPIS for grocery purchase. When the PB goes up by 1 unit that can make the AT go up by 0.369 unit with the standard error of the estimate is 0.081. As the result, efforts to raise benefits of BOPIS such as from the *online information (PB1)*, *offline physical experience (PB2)*, *flexibility (PB3)*, *time and effort saving (PB4)*, *shipping fee saving (PB5)*, *easy returns and refunds (PB6)*, and *product original condition (PB7)* in consumer perception are obviously helpful to generate positive attitudes of consumers towards the service.
- The hypothesis H3 is also verified to be true, the *perceived ease of use* has a positive impact on consumer's attitude towards BOPIS for grocery purchase. When the PE changes by 1 unit, the AT either changes by 0.491 unit with the standard error of the estimate is 0.062. This also means that the adjustment in various dimensions of BOPIS to increase its eases of use will be also an effective way to have more positive attitudes of consumers towards the service, where the elements contributing to the *ease of use* were determined to include the *clear and understandable process (PE1)*, *ease to use online system (PE2)*, *ease to learn using online system (PE3)*, *ease to access the physical store (PE4)*, *simple process (PE5)*, and the *ease to be mastered in BOPIS (PE6)*.
- The hypothesis H2 however does not meet the requirement to conclude that the *perceived risk* has an impact on consumer's attitude towards BOPIS for grocery purchase (p-value > 0.05). Consequently, *privacy risk (PR1)*, *financial risk (PR2)*, *information risk (PR3)*, *product risk (PR4)*, and *performance risk (PR5)* are not really important in consumers' perception which can affect to their attitudes. This is similar to the results of Yang *et al.* (2020), Chen & Chi (2021), Lee (2017) or Victor *et al.* (2018). It can be explained that because those risks are also the risks existed in other

shopping methods, especially the types of e-commerce, consumers can accept those risks or maybe think that BOPIS is not riskier than other shopping methods. For example, the risk of receiving the unsatisfied products are possible with BOPIS, but it is not the problem since consumers think they can check and return the products right at the store. As a result, risks are not the main concern of consumers when using BOPIS in this case.

- The consumer *attitude* is identified to highly influence their *behavioral intention* towards BOPIS for grocery purchase as the hypothesis H4a with the estimate up to 0.860 and the standard error of 0.065. It means that the *attitude* is always the determining factor hugely affecting to the consumer *behavioral intention*. Attitudes were verified to be related to consumer opinion and judgement about BOPIS to see if it is *helpful (AT1)*, *enjoyable (AT2)*, *practical (AT3)*, *efficient (AT4)* or whether it is *a good idea (AT5)* and consumers *like this idea (AT6)* for their grocery purchase. Therefore, if those attitudes are positive, they will lead to favorable behavioral intentions such as consumer will have *intention to try (BI1)*, *intention to use (BI2)*, or *intention to encourage other people to use (BI3)* the service to purchase groceries, they may even *intend to list BOPIS as a top option (BI4)* to purchase groceries and *spread positive word of mouth (BI5)* about the service to other people. Obviously, in case retailers want to gain positive behavioral intentions from consumers, improving their attitudes towards the service is crucial and it is hard to be ignored.

5.2.2.2 Test the mediating effect of the Attitude

Using bootstrapping in Amos to see the direct and indirect effects of *perceived benefit (PB)*, *perceived risk (PR)* and *perceived ease of use (PE)* on the *behavioral intention (BI)* under the mediator *attitude (AT)* with the 95% confidence interval. The output (*appendix 2 section 6*) summarized in *table 5.15* shows that:

- There are indirect effects of PB and PE \rightarrow BI (which zero is not included in the lower and upper bound values) while the direct effects are not significance under the AT mediator, that demonstrates the AT has full mediating effects on the relationships of PB \rightarrow BI and PE \rightarrow BI.
- Meanwhile, the relationship of PR \rightarrow BI is identified with no indirect effect under the AT affecting (the zero is included in the lower and upper bound values). So, it can be concluded that there is no mediating effect of AT on this path and it is not necessary to further consider about the direct effect of PI \rightarrow BI.

Table 5.15 The bootstrapping result of indirect and direct effects of factors on BI under the AT mediator

	Indirect effect			Direct effect			Mediating effect result
	LLC	ULC	Result	LLC	ULC	Result	
PB -> BI	0.221	0.683	yes	0	0	no	Full mediation
PR -> BI	-0.064	0.180	no				no mediation
PE -> BI	0.108	0.561	yes	0	0	no	Full mediation

As the result, the hypothesis H4b is verified to be true when there are the full mediating effects of AT on the relationships of BI with the two other factors (PB and PE). That means the *perceived benefit* and *perceived ease of use* are two factors influencing on the consumer *behavioral intention* but the *attitude* is fully decisive for those influences. *Perceived risk* again shows no effect on consumer *behavioral intention*. Moreover, according to the result of *section 5.2.2.1*, the consumer attitudes towards BOPIS for grocery purchase can strongly decide their behavioral intentions. Therefore, in this case, it one more time emphasizes that increasing consumer attitudes is the most importance and should be given the most attention for any strategy which aims to improve behavioral intentions of consumer towards BOPIS for grocery service.

5.2.2.3 Test the moderating effect of BOPIS knowledge and BOPIS experience

Moderating effects of *BOPIS knowledge* and *BOPIS experience* moderating are investigated by testing the difference in Chi-Square value of constrained and unconstrained models built by multigroup analysis (where BOPIS knowledge includes two groups of consumers: known and unknown; BOPIS experience includes two groups of consumers: experienced and unexperienced). The good fitness indices of constrained and unconstrained models (*appendix 2 section 7*) are all meet requirements in *section 4.1.4.5* demonstrating the models are suitable for analysis.

The result of the test (*table 5.16* built from the output of *appendix 2 section 7*) only finds out the moderating effect of *BOPIS experience* on the PR → AT path which its Chi-Square value difference of the constrained model and unconstrained model is 7.585 (> 3.84).

Table 5.16 The Moderation test for BOPIS knowledge and BOPIS experience

Moderators	Relationships	Overall model	Chi-square	df	p value	Moderating effect result
BOPIS knowledge	PB → AT	Unconstrained	1447.191	736	0.108	No
		Fully constrained	1449.78	737		
		Difference	2.589	1		
	PR → AT	Unconstrained	1447.191	736	0.466	No
		Fully constrained	1447.723	737		
		Difference	0.532	1		
	PE → AT	Unconstrained	1447.191	736	0.512	No
		Fully constrained	1447.62	737		
		Difference	0.429	1		
	AT → BI	Unconstrained	1447.191	736	0.944	No
		Fully constrained	1447.196	737		
		Difference	0.005	1		
BOPIS experience	PB → AT	Unconstrained	1336.436	736	0.419	No
		Fully constrained	1337.09	737		
		Difference	0.654	1		
	PR → AT	Unconstrained	1336.436	736	0.006	Yes
		Fully constrained	1344.021	737		
		Difference	7.585	1		
	PE → AT	Unconstrained	1336.436	736	0.650	No
		Fully constrained	1336.642	737		
		Difference	0.206	1		
	AT → BI	Unconstrained	1336.436	736	0.183	No
		Fully constrained	1338.212	737		
		Difference	1.776	1		

The regression weights of the two groups (BOPIS experienced and unexperienced consumers) indicate the different effects of PR → AT under the *BOPIS experience* moderating effect (table 5.17 built from appendix 2 section 7.9). Specifically, for the group of consumers those with no experience in BOPIS, their *attitude* is positively affected by

their *perceived risk* at the confidential level of 95% (p-value < 0.05). Besides, for the group of consumers those have BOPIS experience, the *perceived risk* does not have a significant effect on the *attitude* at the confidential level of 95%, but if it is just considered at the confidential level of 90% (p-value < 0.1), the *perceived risk* somewhat affects negatively to the *attitude* of consumers towards BOPIS service for grocery purchase.

Table 5.17 Regression weights of unconstrained model for effect of PR → AT under BOPIS experience moderator

Group	Relationship	Estimate	S.E.	p
Experienced	PR → AT	-0.221	0.125	0.077**
Inexperienced	PR → AT	0.177	0.077	0.022***

As the result, the hypothesis H5b regarding the moderating impact of *BOPIS experience* is proved to be true since the *BOPIS experience* can influence on the relationship of the PR→AT. *BOPIS experience* makes the *perceived risk* now has a certain effecting level on the *attitude*. Specifically, consumers with *no BOPIS experience* perceive risks as good and may lead them to have better attitudes towards the service. It is hard to explain why the *perceived risk* can positively affect the *attitude*, it may need to be considered with some other factors, for example like the consumer risk tolerance for better understanding. But anyway this group of consumers is likely to be the target one of grocery BOPIS when it enters to the Vietnam market because these consumers still have more favorable judgement about the service in spite of their perceived risks. Vice versa, consumers with *BOPIS experience* think that risks are bad and make them have negative attitudes towards the service. That means their previous experiences with BOPIS were not really good which make them realize that BOPIS contains potential risks. For this group of consumers, risks are their concern and cause their negative thoughts about the service. Therefore, in order to persuade these experienced consumers, minimizing the risks of BOPIS service in their perception is considered important. Furthermore, because the *attitude* has already been known to determine the *behavioral intention* (the proved hypothesis H4a and H4b), the *BOPIS experience* unfavorably impact on consumer's *attitude* can indirectly restrain consumer's positive *behavioral intention* towards the service.

However, the hypothesis H5a is rejected when no moderating effect of *BOPIS knowledge* is found in the model. That demonstrates knowing and hearing about BOPIS are not enough to significantly effect on the relationships of the factors in model and effect to consumer's *behavioral intention*.

CHAPTER 6: CONCLUSION

6.1 SUMMARY

This study researches on consumer characteristics and perceptions. It firstly came up with the research framework consisting of 5 proposal factors measured by 29 observed variables mainly to understand about the factors affecting to consumers' attitude and behavioral intention towards BOPIS (buy online pick up in-store) for grocery purchase, based on the data collected from 203 Vietnamese consumers. The hypotheses were investigated and some other additional analyses were done yielding some interesting findings:

First of all, the study gives better understandings of Vietnamese consumer characteristics along with their general intention of using BOPIS to purchase groceries. It is implied that BOPIS for grocery purchase is potential but it is just in its early dates and it need more time and efforts to be well adopted in Vietnam market.

Vietnamese consumer *attitude* and *behavioral intention* towards BOPIS for grocery purchase were found out and the factors considered having effects on them which include the *perceived benefit*, *perceived risk*, *perceived ease of use* were also defined by the use of Confirmation Factor Analysis (CFA), all of 29 observed variables were retained and perfectly contributed to the 5 factors as the initial proposal.

Next, the analysis on Structural Equation Model (SEM) found out the causal relationships among factors. The positive impacts of consumer's *perceived benefit* and *perceived ease of use* on the *attitude* were figured out when the *attitude* strongly influences on the consumer's *behavioral intention*. It also indicated the full mediating impacts of the *attitude* in the model which the indirect effects of the *perceived benefit* and *perceived ease of use* on consumer's *behavioral intention* are significant. The study was not able to find out the significant effect of the *perceived risk* on consumer's *attitude* and *behavioral intention* but it found out the moderating effect of *BOPIS experience* on the relationship of *perceived risk* and *attitude*. It led to the implication that consumers with no BOPIS experiences are more possible to adopt the service for their grocery purchase, but for long term application retailers need to care about consumer experiences with the service as well, and the *perceived risk* is not really a factor which should be neglected in this case.

Furthermore, the study did simply estimate consumer intention of using BOPIS to purchase for different categories of grocery and discovered that product category somewhat affects to consumer intention in the case. The fresh and refrigerated food products are deduced that they should be homogenous and ensured the quality to gain higher consumer intention to purchase them with BOPIS.

Overall, all of the factors were determined and the relationships among them were investigated. Retailers can look at them as a source of reference to decide the key factors

that they can manipulate for their BOPIS application and improve their business omnichannel sales.

6.2 IMPLICATION

6.2.1 Vietnamese consumer characteristics and the potential of BOPIS for grocery purchase in Vietnam

According to the data information (*section 5.1.1*), the sample of this study may not represent for the whole population which is Vietnamese consumers in general but it can well represent for the young generation whom many of them are still single and have low or intermediate level of income. They have grocery shopping experience, especially since e-commerce development, many of them have engaged in online shopping for groceries (*section 5.1.2*). But after all, the online shopping is not their priority choice, grocery shopping at hypermarkets or supermarkets are still their first preference (*section 5.1.2*). Therefore, there is a need for a better model of grocery retailing to solve the problems of pure online shopping but still take its advantages, BOPIS could be a potential option.

Then, the BOPIS service is not really new in Vietnam, there are many of consumers have known or heard about the service (*section 5.1.3*). However, it has not widely approached to the consumers, some consumers have BOPIS experiences consisting of OGP (online grocery pickup), but those consumers are not assumed to make up a very large portion (*section 5.1.3*). Thus, BOPIS for groceries is just in its very early dates and it needs more time to be well adopted and applied widely in Vietnam.

6.2.2 Consumer intention to use BOPIS for grocery purchase and the effect of product category

Vietnamese consumers have a certain level of intention to use BOPIS for their grocery purchase in future but it not really high (*section 5.1.4.1*). Especially, consumers seem have less intention of using BOPIS to purchase for the fresh and refrigerated food products which need to be temperature-controlled, compared to the packaged food products which don't need to be temperature-controlled and the non-food products (*section 5.1.4.2*). This is quite understandable because the fresh and refrigerated food products may be sensitive or not homogeneous, consumers obviously concern about the quality of products selected by other people. This problem is not only of pure online shopping but also of BOPIS since consumers are not able to see and select the real items by themselves at the beginning. One feasible solution to this problem is to just sell those types of products in packages with the same packing specifications and minimize the quality variation as much as possible so that consumers feel there is no differences in selecting items by themselves and by staffs. Besides, ensuring those products still be fresh and qualified before they are picked up by customers is also important to help increase the BOPIS using intention for those the fresh and refrigerated food products. However, to increase the positive attitudes

and behavioral intentions towards BOPIS for grocery purchase in general, there are still a lot of other factors need to be concerned.

6.2.3 Factors affecting consumer attitudes and behavioral intentions towards BOPIS for grocery purchase

All analyses in the *section 5.2* are to explore the factors affecting on consumer attitudes and behavioral intentions towards BOPIS for grocery purchase. The analysis results are implied that in addition to the general intention to use, there are various dimensions of consumer behavioral intention which include the *willingness to try the service or use it in the future, intention to encourage other people to use, intention to list BOPIS as a top option to purchase groceries and the intention to spread positive word of mouth* about the service to other people. Those intentions highly depend on the consumer attitudes which are their opinion and judgement about whether the BOPIS is *helpful, enjoyable, practical, efficient* or whether it is *a good idea* and consumers feel *like this idea* for their grocery purchase. If those attitudes are positive, they will probably lead to positive behavioral intentions which are very important and helpful for the adoption of BOPIS in Vietnam for grocery segment in the future. To improve the consumer attitudes and behavioral intention towards grocery BOPIS, the efforts of increasing the perceived benefits and perceived eases of use are essential (*section 5.2.2.1 and section 5.2.2.2*). Specifically:

- Consumers perceive that the benefits of grocery BOPIS consist of *online information, offline physical experience, flexibility, time and effort saving, shipping fee saving, easy returns and refunds*, and even the assurance about the *product original condition* without possible damages incurred by the delivery process. Because those BOPIS benefits integrated by the benefits of both traditionally physical shopping and pure online shopping, it is perceived to be a better shopping method. Those benefits should be ensured otherwise consumers may still keep using their current shopping method rather than change to use BOPIS. For instance, a customer who usually go traditional offline shopping may change to use BOPIS if he sees the service really saves more time and effort, on contrary if he has to take a lot of time for online ordering and then when he comes to the store for the item pickup, he still has to wait for the staff to prepare his order, it is sure he would rather keep traditionally shopping. In short, retailers should have appropriate strategies to ensure those benefits of BOPIS in consumer perception to keep their positive attitudes about the service and gain positive behavioral intentions.
- Additionally, the perceived eases of use determined by the *clear and understandable process, ease to use online system, ease to learn using online system, ease to access the physical store, the simple process*, and the *ease to be mastered* in shopping with BOPIS are the important attributes need to be concerned. Since BOPIS is a new service, a simple process is necessary, if the process of using a

service is too complicated or hard to carry out, consumers of course hesitate to use it. If consumers can be even easily mastered in using this service, for example the BOPIS process is quite similar to their previous online shopping experience, then making BOPIS grocery purchase is also easy for them so they are likely more confident to use the service. Or at least, that process should be clear and understandable so that consumers can easily carry out each stage of the process to make their grocery purchase. Moreover, BOPIS requires consumers to use both online and offline system, so that retailers should have good online system which well designed for consumers easily to use or learn to use it. The offline system should be convenient and able to access as well because consumers will never buy online then come to a physical store which is 100 km far away from their place just for the item pick up.

Perceived risks of consumers with BOPIS are related to the *privacy risk*, *financial risk*, *information risk*, *product risk*, and *performance risk* unsurprisingly were proved to have no significant effect on their attitudes and behavioral intentions towards BOPIS (section 5.2.2.1). However, the relationship of perceived risks and attitudes is somewhat affected by the consumer *BOPIS experience* (section 5.2.2.3). Consumers with no BOPIS experiences are not likely to be negatively affected by perceived risks and may still have favor points of view about the service. But consumers who with BOPIS experiences do not have the same thinking, experienced consumers realize that BOPIS contains potential risks which can prevent them from accepting the service for grocery shopping. Because of this result, it is implied that in case BOPIS is applied in Vietnam, retailers should first concentrate on unexperienced consumers as the target segment because they seem be more potential and more easily to be persuaded. At the same time, there should also be solutions to enhance consumer experiences with BOPIS, especially through minimizing the risks with the service in customer perception, so that retailers can attract and keep consumers using the service in long term. The *perceived risk* now is not a factor could be ignored as the result of the section 5.2.2.1, it somewhat still has a certain affect in the model under the impact of *BOPIS experience*. Fulfilling the commitments on providing good product and service quality, ensuring safety in payment, protecting consumer information, etc. are feasible acts to reduce perceived risks in customer mind, from that enhance their experiences with the service. That is obviously have good impact on consumer attitudes and behavioral intentions and helpful for the adoption of BOPIS in Vietnam for grocery purchase in future.

6.3 COMPARISON TO OTHER PREVIOUS RESEARCHES

This study once again confirms the rationality of theories about consumer behavior of notable scholars mentioned in chapter 2. However, for this study, the research subject is more specific which focuses on using BOPIS to purchase groceries in Vietnam, not just on general intention of using BOPIS or “click and collect” as research of Chen and Chi (2020),

Kim *et al.* (2020), Victor *et al.* (2018), etc. Therefore, it leads to different findings to those previous researches. That is also derived from new things in the way building up the research framework, considered factors and analysis methods applied by the author of this study:

- When many previous researches try to explore variety of factors, this study just focuses on several main factors and try to analyze various dimensions of those factors. For example, while Vitor *et al.* (2018), with the study about click and collect E-tailing services in Malaysia, considered financial risk and product risk independently, this study considers perceived risk as an affecting factor with various dimensions (privacy, financial, information, product, performance). Chen and Chi (2020) considered a lot of factors effect to U.S. consumers' intentions to use BOPIS including the effect of perceived risk, but they just stopped at no effect of perceived risk to BOPIS, this study similarly found out no effect of perceived risk in causal relationship but it still tried to investigate more about the impact of moderator factors (*BOPIS experience*) with the perceived risk and provided a multi-dimensional perspective on the influences of factors. Another difference is that this study emphasizes more on the perceived benefit of BOPIS while the other studies more considered the perceived usefulness of BOPIS.
- This study found out the effects of product category to consumer BOPIS using intention by applying simple ways like *descriptive* or *Paired - samples T test* when there are not many studies had done the same way.
- This study applied modern analysis methods including analyses using outputs of data running in Amos to investigate the relationships of factors (casual, mediating and moderating). That makes the analysis process more simple and the results more comprehensive compared to traditional methods in SPSS.

6.4 RESEARCH LIMITATION AND FUTURE RESEARCH DIRECTION

This study however still has some limitations which include:

- The sample size: Because of restrictions of time, space and funding this study was just able to use the sample of 203 observations to estimate for the parameters of Vietnamese consumers in general. Although the sample meets the basic standards for the estimation but it is still considered small.
- The survey subject: The study would like to investigate on Vietnamese consumers in general but maybe due to the limitation of the online survey method, it mainly approached the group of young consumers. So, the results of this study may just well represent for this group rather than the whole Vietnamese consumers.

- Finally, there are just some main factors supposed important are considered in the model. In reality, maybe there are a lot of other factors can influence on consumers' attitude and behavioral intention, they can even influence to each other and lead to different impact levels. Although it is impossible to consider all of the factors in a study, a study with diverse factors and hypotheses is likely to have more interesting findings.

Therefore, if there is a chance to develop this study or conduct a similar study in the future, the author of this study hopes to extend the sample size and types of survey subject by using a better survey method to increase the reliability for the study, at the same time more potential factors will be considered for more interesting and contributing findings.

REFERENCES

- Alex Rampell (2010). Why online to offline commerce is a trillion - dollar opportunity. <http://www.arampell.org/2010/08/07/why-online-to-offline-commerce-is-a-trillion-dollar-opportunity/> (accessed on 8 December 2021).
- Alexis Damen (2022). What is Buy Online, Pick-Up in Store (BOPIS) in Retail? <https://www.shopify.com/retail/bopis> (accessed on 20 February 2022).
- Amazon website. <https://www.amazon.co.uk/ulp/view> (accessed on 1 February 2022).
- Amazon website.
<https://www.amazon.com/gp/help/customer/display.html?nodeId=202071950>
(accessed on 1 February 2022).
- Arjun Gupta, Rohit Bansal, Atul Bansal (2013). Online Shopping: A Shining Future. *International Journal of Techno-Management Research*, Vol. 01, Issue 01, June 2013. ISSN: 2321-3744
- Baron R. M., & Kenny D. A. (1986). The moderator–mediator variable distinction in social psychological research: Conceptual, strategic, and statistical considerations. *Journal of Personality and Social Psychology*, 51(6), 1173–1182.
- Bentler PM, Chou CH. (1987). Practical issues in structural modeling. *Sociological Methods & Research* Vol. 16, Issue 1, 78–117.
- Beran T. N. and Violato, C. (2010). Structural equation modeling in medical research: a primer. *BMC Research Notes* Vol. 3, Article No. 267, 2010.
- Beran T.N., Violato C. (2010). Structural equation modeling in medical research: a primer. *BMC Research Notes* vol. 3, article 267.
- Bollen KA. (1989). *Structural equations with latent variables*. New York, NY: John Wiley.
- BigCommerce (2021). BOPIS: How Buy Online, Pick-Up in Store is Catering to Consumers' Needs and Boosting Retailers' Bottom Lines. <https://www.bigcommerce.com/articles/offline-to-online/bopis/#bopis-performance-in-the-retail-market> (accessed on 8 December 2021).
- Che-Hung Liu, Yen-Tzu Chen, Santhaya Kittikowit, Tanaporn Hongsuchon & Yi-Jing Chen (2022). Using Unified Theory of Acceptance and Use of Technology to Evaluate the Impact of a Mobile Payment App on the Shopping Intention and Usage Behavior of Middle-Aged Customers. *Frontiers in Psychology* vol. 3, article 830842, March 2022.
- Chu-Ching Wang, Yu-Min Wang & Wei-Heng Chieh (2016). The Moderating Role of Customer Knowledge on the Relationship between Customer Satisfaction and Loyalty. *Journal of Economics, Business and Management*, Vol. 4, No. 4, April 2016.

- Dan J. Kim, Donald L. Ferrin & H. Raghav Rao (2009). Trust and Satisfaction, Two Stepping Stones for Successful E-Commerce Relationships: A Longitudinal Exploration. *Information Systems Research* 20(2), 237-257.
- Darrell Rigby (2011) The Future of Shopping. *Harvard Business Review*. <https://hbr.org/2011/12/the-future-of-shopping> (accessed on 8 December 2021).
- David L Streiner (2005). Finding Our Way: An Introduction to Path Analysis. *The Canadian Journal of Psychiatry* Vol. 50, No. 2, February 2005.
- Davis, F. (1989) Perceived Usefulness, Perceived Ease of Use, and User Acceptance of Information Technology. *MIS Quarterly*, 13, 319-340.
- Dezie Leonarda Warganegara & Roozbeh Babolian Hendijani (2022). Factors That Drive Actual Purchasing of Groceries through E-Commerce Platforms during COVID-19 in Indonesia. *Sustainability* 2022, 14(6), 3235.
- Ellen Van Droogenbroeck & Leo Van Hove (2021). Adoption and Usage of E-Grocery Shopping: A Context-Specific UTAUT2 Model. *Sustainability* 2021, 13(8), 4144.
- Emad Y. Masoud (2013). The Effect of Perceived Risk on Online Shopping in Jordan. *European Journal of Business and Management*, Vol.5, No.6, 2013. ISSN 2222-1905 (Paper). ISSN 2222-2839 (Online).
- Fishbein, M. & Ajzen, I. (1975). *Belief, Attitude, Intention, and Behavior: An Introduction to Theory and Research*. Available: <https://people.umass.edu/aizen/f&a1975.html>
- Fornell C. & Larcker D. F. (1981). Structural Equation Models with Unobservable Variables and Measurement Error: Algebra and Statistics. *Journal of Marketing Research*, 18, 382-388
- Hair J. F., Black W. C., Babin B. J., Anderson R. E. & Tatham R. L. (2006). *Multivariate data analysis 6th Edition*
- Harsha N. Perera (2013). A novel approach to estimating and testing specific mediation effects in educational research: explication and application of Macho and Ledermann's (2011) phantom model approach. *Int. J. Quantitative Research in Education*, Vol. 1, No. 1, 2013.
- Henry F. Kaiser (1974). An index of factorial simplicity. *Psychometrika* vol. 39, pages31–36.
- Hooper D. (2012). *Exploratory Factor Analysis, ARROW@TU Dublin*.
- Icek Ajzen (2000). Attitudes and the Attitude-Behavior Relation: Reasoned and Automatic Processes. *European Review of Social Psychology* 11(1), 1-33.
- Icek Ajzen (2002). Perceived behavioral control, self-efficacy, locus of control, and the theory of planned behavior. *Journal of Applied Social Psychology*, 32(4), 665–683.

- Jason T. Newsom (2020). Multigroup Analysis and Moderation with SEM. Psy 523/623 Structural Equation Modeling spring 2020.
- Ji Bok Chung, Sung Jip Nam (2020). A Study on the User Acceptance of O2O Services: Mediating Effect of Customer Attitude. East Asian Journal of Business Economics 8(3), pp.15-24.
- Johnny R.J. Fontaine (2005). Equivalence. Encyclopedia of Social Measurement vol. 1 pages 803-813.
- Jon Bird (2018) Alibaba's 'New Retail' Revolution: What Is It, And Is It Genuinely New? <https://www.forbes.com/sites/jonbird1/2018/11/18/alibabas-new-retail-revolution-what-is-it-and-is-it-genuinely-new/?sh=532c175a6ad1> (accessed on 1 February 2022).
- Joseph F. Hair Jr., G. Tomas M. Hult, Christian M. Ringle, Marko Sarstedt, Nicholas P. Danks & Soumya Ray (2021). Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM) Using R. ISSN 2662-2866.
- Joseph F. Hair, G. Thomas M. Hult, Christian Ringle, Marko Sarstedt (2014). A Premier on Partial Least Squares Structural Equation Modeling (PLS-SEM). SAGE Publications, Inc.
- Kenneth A. Bollen (2014). Structural Equations with Latent Variables. John Wiley & Sons, Inc.
- Kent State University (2022). SPSS TUTORIALS: PAIRED SAMPLES T TEST. <https://libguides.library.kent.edu/spss/pairedsamplesttest> (accessed on 9 April 2022)
- Kihyung Kim, Sang-Lin Han, Young-Yong Jang & Yun-Chang Shin (2020). The Effects of the Antecedents of “Buy-Online-Pick-Up-In-Store” Service on Consumer’s BOPIS Choice Behavior. Sustainability 2020, 12(23), 9989.
- Kline, R. B. (2005). Principles and practice of structural equation modeling 2nd edition. Guilford publications.
- Kok Wai Tham, Omkar Dastane, Zainudin Johari & Nurlida Binti Ismail (2019). Perceived Risk Factors Affecting Consumers Online Shopping Behaviour. Journal of Asian Finance, Economics and Business, Vol. 6, No. 4 (2019) 249-260.
- Kroger website. <https://www.kroger.com/i/ways-to-shop/pickup> (accessed on 1 February 2022).
- Lauren Leach (2019). A deep dive into the click and collect concept. <https://www.retailcustomerexperience.com/blogs/a-deep-dive-into-the-click-and-collect-concept/> (accessed on 8 December 2021).
- Lee J. Cronbach (1951) Coefficient alpha and the internal structure of tests. Psychometrika 16, pages 297–334.

- Mar Negreiro (2020). The rise of e-commerce and the cashless society. European Parliamentary Research Service (EPRS) March 2020. PE 649.341.
- Mark Ogertschnig & Hans van der Heijden (2004). A Short-Form Measure of Attitude Towards Using A Mobile Information Service. 17th Bled eCommerce Conference eGlobal 2014.
[https://domino.fov.um.si/proceedings.nsf/0/265296bbf7a2e911c1256ee0002ccae4/\\$FILE/10Ogertschnig.pdf](https://domino.fov.um.si/proceedings.nsf/0/265296bbf7a2e911c1256ee0002ccae4/$FILE/10Ogertschnig.pdf)
- Martin Klepek & Radka Bauerová (2020). Why do retail customers hesitate for shopping grocery online? Technological and Economic Development of Economy 2020 Vol. 26 Issue 6, 1444–1462.
- McKinsey & Company (2019). Seizing the fast-growing retail opportunity in Vietnam. <https://www.mckinsey.com/~/media/mckinsey/industries/retail/our%20insights/how%20companies%20can%20seize%20opportunity%20in%20vietnams%20growing%20retail%20market/seizing-the-fast-growing-retail-opportunity-in-vietnam.pdf> (accessed on 1 February 2022).
- MiYoung Lee (2017). The Effects of Using O2O Fashion Mobile Commerce on Consumers' Attitudes and Intentions. Journal of Fashion Business 2017 Vol.21, No.3, 67-79.
- Montri Sangthong (2020). The Effect of the Likert Point Scale and Sample Size on the Efficiency of Parametric and Nonparametric Tests. Thailand Statistician January 2020 18(1), 55-64.
- NielsenIQ (2020). How has covid-19 impact Vietnamese consumers. <https://nielseniq.com/global/en/insights/analysis/2020/how-has-covid-19-impacted-vietnamese-consumers/> (accessed on 1 February 2022).
- Nunnally, J.C. (1978). Psychometric theory 2nd Edition, McGraw-Hill, New York.
- Philip Kotler & Gary Armstrong (2014) Principles of Marketing 15th Edition.
- Pooja Misra, Sushil Baranwal & Manya Jha (2017). Brick and mortar store vs. online shopping experience: a study. International Journal of Information Technology and Management Vol. 16, No. 2, ISSN: 1461-4111.
- Pushpak Singhal & Supriyo Patra (2018). A Study on Consumer Behaviour towards Online Shopping in Kolkata. Journal of Business and Management e-ISSN: 2278-487X, p-ISSN: 2319-7668 PP 91-102. International Business Research Conference, 2018.
- R.Shanthi & Desti Kannaiah (2015). Consumers' Perception on Online Shopping. Journal of Marketing and Consumer Research. An International Peer-reviewed Journal Vol.13, 2015. ISSN 2422-8451.

- Raja Sarkar & Sabyasachi Das (2017). Online Shopping vs Offline Shopping: A Comparative Study. IJSRST Vol. 3, Issue 1, 2017. Print ISSN: 2395-6011, Online ISSN: 2395-602X.
- Randall E. Schumacker, Richard G. Lomax (2016). A Beginner's Guide to Structural Equation Modeling 4th Edition.
- Ricoh USA, Inc. (2020). How retail payment technology is evolving in response to consumer demand? <https://www.ricoh-usa.com/en/insights/articles/retail-payment-technology-going-cashless-and-consumer-demand> (accessed on 20 February 2022).
- Rulin Liu, Weimin Cheng, Yanbin Yua, Qingfeng Xu, Aiwei Jiang, Tong Lv (2019). An impacting factors analysis of miners' unsafe acts based on HFACS-CM and SEM. Process Safety and Environmental Protection Vol. 122, Pages 221-231.
- Sarah Peball (2017). Buying groceries online: consumer perceptions and generational cohorts. A Work Project, presented as part of the requirements for the Award of a Master Degree in Management from the NOVA–School of Business and Economics. https://run.unl.pt/bitstream/10362/23176/1/SarahPeball_2017.pdf
- Shari S. C. Shang, Abby S. T. Yang (2015). The Types of Online to Offline Business Model. Proc. of the Third Intl. Conf. Advances in Computing, Communication and Information Technology- CCIT 2015. ISBN: 978-1-63248-061-3.
- Sukhwinder Kaur and Vikramjit Kaur (2018). Comparative Study on Online Vs. Offline Shopping. International Journal of Creative Research Thoughts (IJCRT) Vol. 6, 2018. ISSN: 2320-2882
- International Journal of Academic Research in Business and Social Sciences Vol. 8, No. 12, Dec, 2018.
- Tan Pei Kian, Alvin Chin Wai Loong & Stany Wee Lian Fong (2018). Customer Purchase Intention on Online Grocery Shopping.
- Target website. <https://www.target.com.au/modal/payment-delivery> (accessed on 1 February 2022).
- Thompson B. (2004). Exploratory and confirmatory factor analysis: Understanding concepts and applications. Washington, DC: American Psychological Association.
- Timothy A. Brown (2015). Confirmatory Factor Analysis for Applied Research 2nd Edition.
- Vietnamplus (2021). Mobile payment users in Vietnam rank third in the world. <https://en.vietnamplus.vn/mobile-payment-users-in-vietnam-rank-third-in-the-world/206472.vnp> (accessed on 20 February 2022).

- Vijay Victor, Nadira Syarfa, Robert Jeyakumar Nathan & Jalal Rajeh Hanaysha (2018). Use of Click and Collect E-tailing Services among Urban Consumers. *Amity Journal of Marketing* 3 (2), 1-16.
- Walgreens website. <https://www.walgreens.com/topic/store/store-pickup.jsp> (accessed on 1 February 2022).
- Walmart website. <https://www.walmart.com/cp/free-store-pickup/2281929> (accessed on 1 February 2022).
- Woodworth R. S. (1929). *Psychology* (revised edition). Henry Holt & Co., New York
- Xinxiang Zhang (2020). Ongoing Trust and Tourism O2O Platform Continuance: A Two-Trustee Involved Model with Moderating Variable. *SAGE Open* Vol. 10, issue 2, May 2020.
- Yi Fan, Jiquan Chen, Gabriela Shirkey, Ranjeet John, Susie R. Wu, Hogeun Park & Changliang Shao (2016). Applications of structural equation modeling (SEM) in ecological studies: an updated review. *Ecological Processes* vol. 5, article 19.
- Yini Chen & Ting Chi (2021). How does channel integration affect consumers' selection of omni-channel shopping methods? An empirical study of U.S. consumers. *Sustainability* 2021, 13(16), 8983.
- Yongqing Yang, Yeming Gong, Lesley Pek Wee Land & Thomas Chesney (2020). Understanding the effects of physical experience and information integration on consumer use of online to offline commerce. *International Journal of Information Management*, Vol. 51, April 2020, 102046.
- Zainudin Awang (2012). *A Handbook on SEM*. Universiti Sultan Zainal Abidin.

Appendix 1
Survey Questionnaire

Factors affecting consumer attitude and behavioral intention towards BOPIS
A case study on grocery purchase in Viet Nam

Introduction:

Buy online pick up in-store (BOPIS), another term for click-and-collect, allows consumers to shop and place orders online and then pick up the purchases in the brick-and-mortar store.

❖ The process of BOPIS:

1. The customer buys online, through the website or mobile app: *the customer determines the type and quantity of items, choose the store location and the time to pick up as well as select the payment method. Then, a confirmation notification is sent to the customer once the order is placed.*
2. The store fulfills the online order.
3. The customer picks up the order at the store.

Directions: Place a " ✓ " mark in the box of your answer.

I. IDENTIFY YOUR GROCERY SHOPPING EXPERIENCE AND BEHAVIOR

Q1. How often do you go shopping for groceries?

- 1. Once a month
- 2. Twice a month
- 3. Three - four times a month
- 4. More than four times a month

Q2. Have you ever purchased groceries online?

- 1. Yes
- 2. No

Q3. If you are going to buy groceries which place you prioritize to go?

- 1. Local Market
- 2. Hypermarket (E.g: Go!, Lotte Mart, AEON, and Co.op Xtra)
- 3. Supermarket and Minimart (E.g: Bach Hoa Xanh, Vinmart)
- 4. Traditional Grocery Stores
- 5. Online stores

Q4. Have you ever known or heard about BOPIS service?

- 1. Yes
- 2. No

Q5. Have you ever used BOPIS service?

- 1. Yes → Q5a. *which type of product did you purchase by BOPIS?*
- 2. No

Q6. What is the probability that you will use BOPIS service for grocery purchase?

- 1. 0%
- 2. Above 0% - 25%
- 3. Above 25% - 50%
- 4. Above 50% - 75%
- 5. Above 75% - 100%

Q7. For products with the following characteristics, which is your degree of consensus to purchase them with BOPIS service?

Question	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
a. Packaged food products which don't need to be temperature-controlled (E.g: instant noodles, canned fish, cookies, candy, ...)							
b. Fresh and refrigerated food products which need to be temperature-controlled (E.g: dairy, raw meat, vegetables, ice cream, ...)							
c. Non-food products (E.g: paper towels, shampoo, detergent, baby care items, ...)							

II. IDENTIFY FACTORS AFFECTING YOUR ATTITUDE AND INTENTION TOWARDS BOPIS FOR GROCERIES

Q8. Please indicate your level of agreement or disagreement with each of these statements. Place a " ✓ " mark in the box of your answer.

Question	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Perceived Benefit							
PB1. Shopping with BOPIS gives me advantage of online information.							

Question	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
PB2. Shopping with BOPIS gives me advantage of offline physical experience.							
PB3. BOPIS provides me with greater flexibility than pure online grocery shopping. I can shop whenever I want and collect my orders at my convenience.							
PB4. BOPIS helps me save more time and effort in terms of searching, selecting products or waiting at the store, compared to traditionally going physical shopping for grocery.							
PB5. BOPIS helps me save shipping fees compared to pure online shopping.							
PB6. It is easier for me to ask for changes or product returns and refunds than pure online shopping if I choose BOPIS.							
PB7. By using BOPIS, I am able to possess the product in its original condition right at the store without worrying about possible damages by the delivery process.							
Perceived Risk							
PR1. My privacy information may easily be exposed to the use of BOPIS shopping.							

Question	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
PR2. Making an online payment process may lead to the high potential of monetary losses such as from the exposure of checking account and passwords or being hacked by someone.							
PR3. The online information (e.g: inventory, product descriptions, promotions, etc.) can be different from the reality at the store.							
PR4. The actual products of perishable groceries (e.g: vegetables, fruits, etc.) may be in low-quality or don't meet my expectations.							
PR5. My order may not be fulfilled exactly and punctually when I come to collect it.							
Perceived Ease of Use							
PE1. The process of BOPIS is clear and understandable.							
PE2. It is easy for me to use the online system to make orders.							
PE3. It is easy for me to learn using online system to make orders.							
PE4. It is easy for me to access and pick up the product at the physical store.							
PE5. The whole process of purchasing with BOPIS is simple to me.							
PE6. I can be mastered at shopping with BOPIS.							

Question	Strongly Disagree	Disagree	Somewhat disagree	Neutral	Somewhat agree	Agree	Strongly Agree
Attitude towards BOPIS for grocery purchase							
AT1. I feel that using BOPIS to shop for groceries is helpful.							
AT2. I feel that using BOPIS to shop for groceries is enjoyable.							
AT3. I feel that using BOPIS to shop for groceries is practical.							
AT4. I feel that using BOPIS to shop for groceries is efficient.							
AT5. I feel that using BOPIS to shop for groceries is a good idea.							
AT6. I like the idea of using BOPIS to purchase groceries.							
Behavioral intention towards BOPIS for grocery purchase							
BI1. I am willing to try using BOPIS to purchase groceries.							
BI2. I think I would use BOPIS to purchase groceries in the future.							
BI3. I will encourage other people to use BOPIS service to purchase groceries if after using I feel satisfied.							
BI4. I maybe list BOPIS as one of my top options to purchase groceries in the future.							
BI5. I will probably spread positive word of mouth about BOPIS to other people.							

III. PERSONAL INFORMATION

Q9. How old are you?

- 1. < 22 years old
- 2. 22 – 34 years old
- 3. \geq 35 years old

Q10. What is your gender?

- 1. Male
- 2. Female
- 3. Others

Q11. What is your marital status?

- 1. Single
- 2. Married, no children
- 3. Married, have children

Q12. What is your education level?

- 1. Less Than High School / High School Diploma
- 2. College/ Bachelor's Degree
- 3. Postgraduate Degree

Q13. Which is your income level? (1.000.000 VND ~ 43 USD)

- 1. <8.000.000 VND
- 2. 8.000.000 – under 20.000.000 VND
- 3. \geq 20.000.000 VND

Thank you for sharing your thoughts with us!!!

Appendix 2

Data output

1. Data description

Q1

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Three - four times a month	65	32.0	32.0	32.0
More than four times a month	97	47.8	47.8	79.8
Once a month	18	8.9	8.9	88.7
Twice a month	23	11.3	11.3	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

Q2

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid No	63	31.0	31.0	31.0
Yes	140	69.0	69.0	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

Q3

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Hypermarket (E.g: Go!, Lotte Mart, AEON, and Co.op Xtra)	74	36.5	36.5	36.5
Local Market	21	10.3	10.3	46.8
Online stores	7	3.4	3.4	50.2
Supermarket and Minimart (E.g: Bach Hoa Xanh, Vinmart)	69	34.0	34.0	84.2
Traditional Grocery Stores	32	15.8	15.8	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

Q4

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
No	42	20.7	20.7	20.7
Valid Yes	161	79.3	79.3	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

Q5

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
No	125	61.6	61.6	61.6
Valid Yes	78	38.4	38.4	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

Q6

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
0	11	5.4	5.4	5.4
Above 0% - 25%	59	29.1	29.1	34.5
Valid Above 25% - 50%	80	39.4	39.4	73.9
Above 50% - 75%	36	17.7	17.7	91.6
Above 75% - 100%	17	8.4	8.4	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

Q7a

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Agree	75	36.9	36.9	36.9
Disagree	11	5.4	5.4	42.4
Neutral	35	17.2	17.2	59.6
Valid Somewhat agree	21	10.3	10.3	70.0
Somewhat disagree	11	5.4	5.4	75.4
Strongly Agree	39	19.2	19.2	94.6
Strongly Disagree	11	5.4	5.4	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

Q7b

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Agree	43	21.2	21.2	21.2
Disagree	23	11.3	11.3	32.5
Neutral	47	23.2	23.2	55.7
Somewhat agree	35	17.2	17.2	72.9
Somewhat disagree	23	11.3	11.3	84.2
Strongly Agree	18	8.9	8.9	93.1
Strongly Disagree	14	6.9	6.9	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

Q7c

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Agree	74	36.5	36.5	36.5
Disagree	9	4.4	4.4	40.9
Neutral	29	14.3	14.3	55.2
Somewhat agree	25	12.3	12.3	67.5
Somewhat disagree	11	5.4	5.4	72.9
Strongly Agree	45	22.2	22.2	95.1
Strongly Disagree	10	4.9	4.9	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

PB1

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1	11	5.4	5.4	5.4
2	8	3.9	3.9	9.4
3	14	6.9	6.9	16.3
4	29	14.3	14.3	30.5
5	33	16.3	16.3	46.8
6	80	39.4	39.4	86.2
7	28	13.8	13.8	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

PB3

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1	16	7.9	7.9	7.9
2	9	4.4	4.4	12.3
3	18	8.9	8.9	21.2
4	23	11.3	11.3	32.5
5	23	11.3	11.3	43.8
6	74	36.5	36.5	80.3
7	40	19.7	19.7	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

PB4

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1	18	8.9	8.9	8.9
2	9	4.4	4.4	13.3
3	13	6.4	6.4	19.7
4	18	8.9	8.9	28.6
5	20	9.9	9.9	38.4
6	76	37.4	37.4	75.9
7	49	24.1	24.1	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

PB5

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1	19	9.4	9.4	9.4
2	14	6.9	6.9	16.3
3	19	9.4	9.4	25.6
4	26	12.8	12.8	38.4
5	29	14.3	14.3	52.7
6	60	29.6	29.6	82.3
7	36	17.7	17.7	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

PB6

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1	18	8.9	8.9	8.9
2	15	7.4	7.4	16.3
3	15	7.4	7.4	23.6
4	33	16.3	16.3	39.9
5	21	10.3	10.3	50.2
6	69	34.0	34.0	84.2
7	32	15.8	15.8	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

PB7

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1	20	9.9	9.9	9.9
2	5	2.5	2.5	12.3
3	17	8.4	8.4	20.7
4	21	10.3	10.3	31.0
5	24	11.8	11.8	42.9
6	70	34.5	34.5	77.3
7	46	22.7	22.7	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

PR1

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1	14	6.9	6.9	6.9
2	12	5.9	5.9	12.8
3	25	12.3	12.3	25.1
4	48	23.6	23.6	48.8
5	32	15.8	15.8	64.5
6	57	28.1	28.1	92.6
7	15	7.4	7.4	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

PR2

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1	17	8.4	8.4	8.4
2	21	10.3	10.3	18.7
3	19	9.4	9.4	28.1
4	31	15.3	15.3	43.3
5	35	17.2	17.2	60.6
6	60	29.6	29.6	90.1
7	20	9.9	9.9	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

PR3

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1	16	7.9	7.9	7.9
2	15	7.4	7.4	15.3
3	16	7.9	7.9	23.2
4	36	17.7	17.7	40.9
5	38	18.7	18.7	59.6
6	58	28.6	28.6	88.2
7	24	11.8	11.8	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

PR4

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1	14	6.9	6.9	6.9
2	12	5.9	5.9	12.8
3	16	7.9	7.9	20.7
4	26	12.8	12.8	33.5
5	35	17.2	17.2	50.7
6	65	32.0	32.0	82.8
7	35	17.2	17.2	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

PR5

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1	14	6.9	6.9	6.9
2	15	7.4	7.4	14.3
3	14	6.9	6.9	21.2
4	31	15.3	15.3	36.5
5	43	21.2	21.2	57.6
6	61	30.0	30.0	87.7
7	25	12.3	12.3	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

PE1

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1	12	5.9	5.9	5.9
2	3	1.5	1.5	7.4
3	12	5.9	5.9	13.3
4	45	22.2	22.2	35.5
5	41	20.2	20.2	55.7
6	72	35.5	35.5	91.1
7	18	8.9	8.9	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

PE2

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1	12	5.9	5.9	5.9
2	9	4.4	4.4	10.3
3	7	3.4	3.4	13.8
4	40	19.7	19.7	33.5
5	35	17.2	17.2	50.7
6	75	36.9	36.9	87.7
7	25	12.3	12.3	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

PE3

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1	13	6.4	6.4	6.4
2	5	2.5	2.5	8.9
3	12	5.9	5.9	14.8
4	26	12.8	12.8	27.6
5	39	19.2	19.2	46.8
6	75	36.9	36.9	83.7
7	33	16.3	16.3	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

PE4

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1	13	6.4	6.4	6.4
2	7	3.4	3.4	9.9
3	12	5.9	5.9	15.8
4	33	16.3	16.3	32.0
5	37	18.2	18.2	50.2
6	79	38.9	38.9	89.2
7	22	10.8	10.8	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

PE5

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1	14	6.9	6.9	6.9
2	8	3.9	3.9	10.8
3	12	5.9	5.9	16.7
4	42	20.7	20.7	37.4
5	29	14.3	14.3	51.7
6	73	36.0	36.0	87.7
7	25	12.3	12.3	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

PE6

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1	11	5.4	5.4	5.4
2	7	3.4	3.4	8.9
3	8	3.9	3.9	12.8
4	35	17.2	17.2	30.0
5	39	19.2	19.2	49.3
6	71	35.0	35.0	84.2
7	32	15.8	15.8	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

AT1

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1	9	4.4	4.4	4.4
2	9	4.4	4.4	8.9
3	8	3.9	3.9	12.8
4	49	24.1	24.1	36.9
5	30	14.8	14.8	51.7
6	70	34.5	34.5	86.2
7	28	13.8	13.8	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

AT2

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1	11	5.4	5.4	5.4
2	13	6.4	6.4	11.8
3	10	4.9	4.9	16.7
4	50	24.6	24.6	41.4
5	35	17.2	17.2	58.6
6	60	29.6	29.6	88.2
7	24	11.8	11.8	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

AT3

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1	11	5.4	5.4	5.4
2	12	5.9	5.9	11.3
3	15	7.4	7.4	18.7
4	34	16.7	16.7	35.5
5	36	17.7	17.7	53.2
6	66	32.5	32.5	85.7
7	29	14.3	14.3	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

AT4

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1	9	4.4	4.4	4.4
2	11	5.4	5.4	9.9
3	16	7.9	7.9	17.7
4	44	21.7	21.7	39.4
5	40	19.7	19.7	59.1
6	60	29.6	29.6	88.7
7	23	11.3	11.3	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

AT5

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1	11	5.4	5.4	5.4
2	10	4.9	4.9	10.3
3	8	3.9	3.9	14.3
4	36	17.7	17.7	32.0
5	31	15.3	15.3	47.3
6	72	35.5	35.5	82.8
7	35	17.2	17.2	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

AT6

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1	9	4.4	4.4	4.4
2	10	4.9	4.9	9.4
3	14	6.9	6.9	16.3
4	38	18.7	18.7	35.0
5	31	15.3	15.3	50.2
6	71	35.0	35.0	85.2
7	30	14.8	14.8	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

BI1

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1	11	5.4	5.4	5.4
2	9	4.4	4.4	9.9
3	12	5.9	5.9	15.8
4	37	18.2	18.2	34.0
5	36	17.7	17.7	51.7
6	67	33.0	33.0	84.7
7	31	15.3	15.3	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

BI2

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1	12	5.9	5.9	5.9
2	9	4.4	4.4	10.3
3	12	5.9	5.9	16.3
4	36	17.7	17.7	34.0
5	36	17.7	17.7	51.7
6	65	32.0	32.0	83.7
7	33	16.3	16.3	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

BI3

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1	13	6.4	6.4	6.4
2	8	3.9	3.9	10.3
3	10	4.9	4.9	15.3
4	40	19.7	19.7	35.0
5	31	15.3	15.3	50.2
6	64	31.5	31.5	81.8
7	37	18.2	18.2	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

BI4

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1	12	5.9	5.9	5.9
2	13	6.4	6.4	12.3
3	20	9.9	9.9	22.2
4	40	19.7	19.7	41.9
5	36	17.7	17.7	59.6
6	62	30.5	30.5	90.1
7	20	9.9	9.9	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

BI5

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid 1	12	5.9	5.9	5.9
2	9	4.4	4.4	10.3
3	13	6.4	6.4	16.7
4	43	21.2	21.2	37.9
5	41	20.2	20.2	58.1
6	62	30.5	30.5	88.7
7	23	11.3	11.3	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

Q9

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid >= 35 years old	17	8.4	8.4	8.4
< 22 years old	18	8.9	8.9	17.2
22 - 34 years old	168	82.8	82.8	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

Q10

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Female	128	63.1	63.1	63.1
Male	74	36.5	36.5	99.5
Others	1	.5	.5	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

Q11

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid Married, have children	29	14.3	14.3	14.3
Married, no children	16	7.9	7.9	22.2
Single	158	77.8	77.8	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

Q12

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
Valid College/ Bachelor's Degree	121	59.6	59.6	59.6
Less Than High School / High School Diploma	27	13.3	13.3	72.9
Postgraduate Degree	55	27.1	27.1	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

Q13

	Frequency	Percent	Valid Percent	Cumulative Percent
>= 20.000.000 VND	27	13.3	13.3	13.3
< 8.000.000 VND	78	38.4	38.4	51.7
8.000.000 - under 20.000.000 VND	98	48.3	48.3	100.0
Total	203	100.0	100.0	

Descriptive Statistics for variables

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
PB1	203	1	7	5.05	1.611
PB2	203	1	7	4.50	1.798
PB3	203	1	7	5.02	1.816
PB4	203	1	7	5.15	1.870
PB5	203	1	7	4.75	1.893
PB6	203	1	7	4.77	1.864
PB7	203	1	7	5.06	1.871
PR1	203	1	7	4.49	1.642
PR2	203	1	7	4.51	1.806
PR3	203	1	7	4.65	1.752
PR4	203	1	7	4.93	1.760
PR5	203	1	7	4.76	1.717
PE1	203	1	7	4.91	1.500
PE2	203	1	7	4.98	1.598
PE3	203	1	7	5.12	1.622
PE4	203	1	7	4.97	1.603
PE5	203	1	7	4.89	1.660
PE6	203	1	7	5.09	1.578
AT1	203	1	7	4.99	1.554
AT2	203	1	7	4.78	1.618
AT3	203	1	7	4.90	1.662
AT4	203	1	7	4.81	1.566
AT5	203	1	7	5.08	1.642
AT6	203	1	7	5.00	1.603
BI1	203	1	7	4.99	1.624
BI2	203	1	7	4.98	1.656
BI3	203	1	7	5.01	1.683
BI4	203	1	7	4.68	1.650
BI5	203	1	7	4.82	1.598
Valid N (listwise)	203				

Descriptive Statistics for Q7

	N	Minimum	Maximum	Mean	Std. Deviation
Q7a	203	1	7	5.09	1.699
Q7b	203	1	7	4.32	1.709
Q7c	203	1	7	5.23	1.661
Valid N (listwise)	203				

2. Paired Samples T Test

Paired Samples Test

	Paired Differences					t	df	Sig. (2-tailed)
	Mean	Std. Deviation	Std. Error Mean	95% Confidence Interval of the Difference				
				Lower	Upper			
Pair 1 Q7a - Q7b	.778	1.792	.126	.530	1.026	6.187	202	.000
Pair 2 Q7b - Q7c	-.911	1.738	.122	-1.152	-.671	-7.469	202	.000
Pair 3 Q7a - Q7c	-.133	1.155	.081	-.293	.027	-1.641	202	.102

3. Cronbach's Alpha

➤ Perceived benefit (PB):

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.931	7

Item-Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
PB1	29.25	88.813	.769	.922
PB2	29.81	88.839	.670	.931
PB3	29.29	84.255	.816	.917
PB4	29.15	83.467	.814	.917
PB5	29.55	84.021	.783	.920
PB6	29.54	84.418	.784	.920
PB7	29.25	83.157	.823	.916

➤ Perceived Risk (PR):

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.928	5

Item-Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
PR1	18.84	40.579	.731	.927
PR2	18.83	37.084	.828	.909
PR3	18.68	37.672	.828	.909
PR4	18.41	37.708	.821	.910
PR5	18.58	37.711	.849	.905

➤ Perceived Ease of Use (PE):

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.961	6

Item-Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
PE1	25.04	54.755	.883	.953
PE2	24.98	53.688	.870	.954
PE3	24.84	53.325	.872	.954
PE4	24.99	53.178	.893	.952
PE5	25.07	52.956	.865	.955
PE6	24.86	53.773	.879	.953

➤ Attitude (AT):

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.967	6

Item-Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
AT1	24.56	57.099	.874	.963
AT2	24.77	56.443	.863	.964
AT3	24.65	55.654	.872	.964
AT4	24.74	56.053	.919	.959
AT5	24.47	54.785	.928	.958
AT6	24.56	55.684	.911	.959

➤ Behavioral Intention (BI):

Reliability Statistics

Cronbach's Alpha	N of Items
.964	5

Item-Total Statistics

	Scale Mean if Item Deleted	Scale Variance if Item Deleted	Corrected Item-Total Correlation	Cronbach's Alpha if Item Deleted
BI1	19.49	38.479	.883	.957
BI2	19.50	37.528	.919	.952
BI3	19.47	37.567	.898	.955
BI4	19.80	38.162	.884	.957
BI5	19.66	38.494	.901	.955

4. CFA

4.1 Factor Analysis result:

KMO and Bartlett's Test

Kaiser-Meyer-Olkin Measure of Sampling Adequacy.		.947
Approx. Chi-Square		6909.548
Bartlett's Test of Sphericity	df	406
	Sig.	.000

Total Variance Explained

Component	Initial Eigenvalues			Extraction Sums of Squared Loadings			Rotation Sums of Squared Loadings		
	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %	Total	% of Variance	Cumulative %
1	16.075	55.431	55.431	16.075	55.431	55.431	5.154	17.771	17.771
2	3.156	10.883	66.314	3.156	10.883	66.314	5.055	17.430	35.201
3	1.760	6.069	72.383	1.760	6.069	72.383	4.996	17.229	52.429
4	1.426	4.918	77.302	1.426	4.918	77.302	4.262	14.698	67.127
5	1.189	4.101	81.402	1.189	4.101	81.402	4.140	14.276	81.402
6	.598	2.063	83.465						
7	.523	1.802	85.267						
8	.488	1.684	86.951						
9	.392	1.353	88.304						
10	.386	1.332	89.636						
11	.319	1.099	90.735						
12	.289	.997	91.732						
13	.229	.790	92.522						
14	.224	.772	93.294						
15	.214	.738	94.032						
16	.206	.709	94.741						
17	.185	.637	95.378						
18	.178	.614	95.992						
19	.164	.564	96.556						
20	.151	.521	97.078						
21	.142	.491	97.568						
22	.129	.446	98.015						
23	.115	.396	98.411						
24	.106	.365	98.776						
25	.090	.309	99.085						
26	.080	.277	99.362						
27	.073	.253	99.615						
28	.064	.221	99.836						
29	.047	.164	100.000						

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotated Component Matrix^a

	Component				
	1	2	3	4	5
PB1	.704				
PB2	.684				
PB3	.694				
PB4	.723				
PB5	.765				
PB6	.781				
PB7	.774				
PR1					.809
PR2					.883
PR3					.841
PR4					.834
PR5					.855
PE1		.768			
PE2		.772			
PE3		.775			
PE4		.798			
PE5		.725			
PE6		.773			
AT1			.748		
AT2			.791		
AT3			.751		
AT4			.785		
AT5			.775		
AT6			.760		
BI1				.733	
BI2				.776	
BI3				.752	
BI4				.775	
BI5				.792	

Extraction Method: Principal Component Analysis.

Rotation Method: Varimax with Kaiser Normalization.

4.2 Measurement Model and outputs used to create validity and reliability estimates:

➤ *The original measurement model:*

Covariances (original measurement model):

	M.I.	Par Change		M.I.	Par Change		M.I.	Par Change
e7 <--> AT	4.202	-.066	e23 <--> PE	10.362	-.055	e19 <--> e21	4.347	.092
e7 <--> PE	5.311	.076	e23 <--> e24	28.331	.117	e20 <--> e19	13.048	.162
e6 <--> e7	44.676	.599	e22 <--> PR	5.789	-.067	e17 <--> BI	4.593	.051
e28 <--> AT	6.116	.057	e22 <--> e23	4.197	-.048	e17 <--> e18	22.435	.199
e28 <--> e29	58.175	.296	e21 <--> e24	6.251	-.083	e15 <--> e17	8.355	-.128
e27 <--> AT	4.438	-.045	e21 <--> e28	5.631	.106	e13 <--> e28	7.334	-.103
e27 <--> PE	4.767	.048	e21 <--> e25	4.293	-.085	e13 <--> e27	7.685	.097
e27 <--> PR	5.400	.075	e21 <--> e23	4.657	-.068	e14 <--> e18	9.214	-.124
e27 <--> e28	4.323	-.080	e21 <--> e22	8.932	.106	e14 <--> e28	12.051	.149
e25 <--> e29	17.253	-.148	e19 <--> e24	15.387	-.124	e14 <--> e26	8.247	-.101
e26 <--> e29	11.801	-.107	e19 <--> e29	15.324	-.153	e14 <--> e23	15.219	-.120
e26 <--> e28	7.150	-.091	e19 <--> e25	9.875	.123	e14 <--> e21	4.107	.091
e26 <--> e25	28.882	.168	e19 <--> e26	4.716	.075	e14 <--> e20	10.284	.147

	M.I.	Par Change		M.I.	Par Change		M.I.	Par Change
e14 <--> e17	7.148	-.118	e10 <--> e13	8.493	-.136	e3 <--> BI	4.503	.062
e14 <--> e15	13.878	.159	e10 <--> e11	7.658	-.170	e3 <--> e7	7.657	-.206
e12 <--> e23	4.642	.072	e8 <--> e12	9.659	-.208	e3 <--> e6	12.179	-.285
e11 <--> e27	12.064	.166	e9 <--> e24	6.271	.111	e3 <--> e28	4.853	.120
e11 <--> e22	4.229	-.085	e9 <--> e12	7.636	-.170	e3 <--> e8	9.820	.250
e11 <--> e20	4.394	-.116	e9 <--> e8	28.067	.454	e3 <--> e4	13.111	.254
e11 <--> e12	8.167	.153	e5 <--> e6	9.049	.293	e2 <--> e29	4.198	-.103
e10 <--> BI	4.072	-.057	e5 <--> e19	4.432	-.135	e2 <--> e19	8.802	.161
e10 <--> e24	8.889	-.117	e5 <--> e14	7.868	-.182	e2 <--> e5	7.537	-.225
e10 <--> e22	8.987	.125	e5 <--> e12	4.922	.155	e2 <--> e4	5.094	.161
e10 <--> e19	10.695	.169	e5 <--> e8	9.651	-.295	e2 <--> e3	7.100	.183
e10 <--> e20	5.085	.125	e4 <--> e7	7.280	-.209	e1 <--> e15	4.108	-.149
e10 <--> e16	6.529	.124	e4 <--> e6	10.646	-.277	e1 <--> e4	4.851	-.211

➤ The improved measurement model:

Chi-square/df=2.027 ; RMSEA=.071 ;
 NFI=.898 ; IFI=.946 ;
 CFI=.946 ; PGFI=.668

Regression Weights:

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
PB2	<---	PB	1.725	.160	10.752	***	par_1
PB1	<---	PB	1.869	.133	14.083	***	par_2
PB3	<---	PB	2.270	.143	15.865	***	par_3
PB4	<---	PB	2.323	.148	15.711	***	par_4
PB5	<---	PB	2.118	.159	13.300	***	par_5
PR2	<---	PR	2.128	.148	14.360	***	par_6
PR1	<---	PR	1.715	.143	11.995	***	par_7
PR3	<---	PR	2.159	.140	15.477	***	par_8
PR4	<---	PR	2.177	.140	15.562	***	par_9
PR5	<---	PR	2.204	.133	16.568	***	par_10
PE2	<---	PE	2.005	.124	16.111	***	par_11
PE1	<---	PE	1.914	.115	16.596	***	par_12
PE3	<---	PE	2.042	.126	16.221	***	par_13
PE4	<---	PE	2.059	.123	16.797	***	par_14
PE5	<---	PE	2.087	.129	16.166	***	par_15
AT2	<---	AT	1.986	.127	15.578	***	par_16
AT1	<---	AT	1.929	.122	15.858	***	par_17
AT3	<---	AT	2.070	.130	15.952	***	par_18
AT4	<---	AT	2.059	.118	17.516	***	par_19
AT5	<---	AT	2.218	.120	18.405	***	par_20
BI2	<---	BI	2.234	.122	18.335	***	par_21
BI1	<---	BI	2.124	.123	17.324	***	par_22
BI3	<---	BI	2.183	.128	17.063	***	par_23
BI4	<---	BI	2.021	.131	15.478	***	par_24
BI5	<---	BI	1.987	.125	15.859	***	par_25
PB6	<---	PB	1.978	.161	12.282	***	par_26
PB7	<---	PB	2.128	.156	13.625	***	par_27
PE6	<---	PE	2.001	.122	16.400	***	par_28
AT6	<---	AT	2.138	.119	17.990	***	par_29

Standardized Regression Weights:

			Estimate
PB2	<---	PB	.680
PB1	<---	PB	.822
PB3	<---	PB	.886
PB4	<---	PB	.881
PB5	<---	PB	.793
PR2	<---	PR	.835
PR1	<---	PR	.740
PR3	<---	PR	.874
PR4	<---	PR	.877
PR5	<---	PR	.910
PE2	<---	PE	.889

			Estimate
PE1	<---	PE	.905
PE3	<---	PE	.893
PE4	<---	PE	.911
PE5	<---	PE	.891
AT2	<---	AT	.870
AT1	<---	AT	.880
AT3	<---	AT	.883
AT4	<---	AT	.932
AT5	<---	AT	.957
BI2	<---	BI	.957
BI1	<---	BI	.927
BI3	<---	BI	.920
BI4	<---	BI	.868
BI5	<---	BI	.881
PB6	<---	PB	.752
PB7	<---	PB	.806
PE6	<---	PE	.899
AT6	<---	AT	.946

Correlations: (Group number 1 - Default model)

			Estimate
PB	<-->	PR	.510
PB	<-->	PE	.710
PB	<-->	AT	.712
PB	<-->	BI	.690
PR	<-->	PE	.392
PR	<-->	AT	.402
PR	<-->	BI	.389
PE	<-->	AT	.743
PE	<-->	BI	.769
AT	<-->	BI	.771
e6	<-->	e7	.515
e28	<-->	e29	.584

Implied (for all variables) Correlations (Group number 1 - Default model)

	BI	AT	PE	PR	PB
BI	1.000				
AT	.771	1.000			
PE	.769	.743	1.000		
PR	.389	.402	.392	1.000	
PB	.690	.712	.710	.510	1.000

5. Causal model

Chi-square/df=2.125 ; RMSEA=.075 ;
 NFI=.893 ; IFI=.940 ;
 CFI=.940 ; PGFI=.667

Regression Weights: (Group number 1 - Default model)

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
AT	<---	PB	.369	.081	4.539	***	par_26
AT	<---	PR	.037	.062	.587	.557	par_27
AT	<---	PE	.491	.073	6.686	***	par_28
BI	<---	AT	.860	.065	13.239	***	par_29

Covariances: (Group number 1 - Default model)

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
PB	<-->	PR	.818	.149	5.499	***	par_31
PB	<-->	PE	1.271	.175	7.249	***	par_32
PR	<-->	PE	.643	.138	4.676	***	par_33
e28	<-->	e29	.357	.060	5.963	***	par_25
e6	<-->	e7	.691	.125	5.539	***	par_30

6. Outputs for testing mediating effect of the Attitude

Indirect Effects - Lower Bounds (BC)

	PE	PR	PB	AT	BI
AT	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
BI	.221	-.064	.108	.000	.000

Indirect Effects - Upper Bounds (BC)

	PE	PR	PB	AT	BI
AT	.000	.000	.000	.000	.000
BI	.683	.180	.561	.000	.000

Indirect Effects - Two Tailed Significance (BC)

	PE	PR	PB	AT	BI
AT
BI	.005	.450	.010

Direct Effects - Lower Bounds (BC)

	PE	PR	PB	AT	BI
AT	.251	-.075	.130	.000	.000
BI	.000	.000	.000	.700	.000

Direct Effects - Upper Bounds (BC)

	PE	PR	PB	AT	BI
AT	.761	.242	.667	.000	.000
BI	.000	.000	.000	.983	.000

Direct Effects - Two Tailed Significance (BC)

	PE	PR	PB	AT	BI
AT	.005	.450	.011
BI009	...

7. Outputs for testing moderating effects of BOPIS knowledge and experience

7.1 BOPIS knowledge on PB → AT path

Constrained model:

Unconstrained model:

CMIN

Model	NPAR	CMIN	DF	P	CMIN/DF
Constrained	133	1449.780	737	.000	1.967
Unconstrained	134	1447.191	736	.000	1.966
Saturated model	870	.000	0		
Independence model	58	8016.249	812	.000	9.872

7.2 BOPIS knowledge on PR → AT path

Constrained model:

Unconstrained model:

CMIN

Model	NPAR	CMIN	DF	P	CMIN/DF
Constrained	133	1447.723	737	.000	1.964
Unconstrained	134	1447.191	736	.000	1.966
Saturated model	870	.000	0		
Independence model	58	8016.249	812	.000	9.872

7.3 BOPIS knowledge on PE → AT path

Constrained model:

Unconstrained model:

CMIN

Model	NPAR	CMIN	DF	P	CMIN/DF
Constrained	133	1447.620	737	.000	1.964
Unconstrained	134	1447.191	736	.000	1.966
Saturated model	870	.000	0		
Independence model	58	8016.249	812	.000	9.872

7.4 BOPIS knowledge on AT → BI path

Constrained model:

Unconstrained model:

CMIN

Model	NPAR	CMIN	DF	P	CMIN/DF
Constrained	133	1447.196	737	.000	1.964
Unconstrained	134	1447.191	736	.000	1.966
Saturated model	870	.000	0		
Independence model	58	8016.249	812	.000	9.872

7.5 BOPIS experience on PB → AT path

Constrained model:

Unconstrained model:

CMIN

Model	NPAR	CMIN	DF	P	CMIN/DF
Constrained	133	1337.090	737	.000	1.814
Unconstrained	134	1336.436	736	.000	1.816
Saturated model	870	.000	0		
Independence model	58	7918.012	812	.000	9.751

7.6 BOPIS experience on PR → AT path

Constrained model:

Unconstrained model:

CMIN

Model	NPAR	CMIN	DF	P	CMIN/DF
Constrained	133	1344.021	737	.000	1.824
Unconstrained	134	1336.436	736	.000	1.816
Saturated model	870	.000	0		
Independence model	58	7918.012	812	.000	9.751

7.7 BOPIS experience on PE → AT path

Constrained model:

Unconstrained model:

CMIN

Model	NPAR	CMIN	DF	P	CMIN/DF
Constrained	133	1336.642	737	.000	1.814
Unconstrained	134	1336.436	736	.000	1.816
Saturated model	870	.000	0		
Independence model	58	7918.012	812	.000	9.751

7.8 BOPIS experience on AT → BI path

Constrained model:

Unconstrained model:

CMIN

Model	NPAR	CMIN	DF	P	CMIN/DF
Constrained	133	1338.212	737	.000	1.816
Unconstrained	134	1336.436	736	.000	1.816
Saturated model	870	.000	0		
Independence model	58	7918.012	812	.000	9.751

7.9 Regression weights of BOPIS Experienced and Inexperienced consumer group

Regression Weights: (EXP - Unconstrained)

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
AT	<---	PB	.508	.142	3.576	***	par_29
AT	<---	PR	-.221	.125	-1.771	.077	EXP
AT	<---	PE	.395	.105	3.774	***	par_30
BI	<---	AT	.748	.106	7.084	***	par_31

Regression Weights: (UNEXP - Unconstrained)

			Estimate	S.E.	C.R.	P	Label
AT	<---	PB	.368	.102	3.614	***	par_61
AT	<---	PR	.177	.077	2.295	.022	UNEXP
AT	<---	PE	.462	.104	4.456	***	par_62
BI	<---	AT	.930	.085	10.957	***	par_63